

1 **Anti-rotavirus properties and mechanisms of selected Gram-positive and Gram-**
2 **negative probiotics on polarized human colonic (HT-29) cells**

3 Anand Kumar^{a,b}, Yosra A. Helmy^a, Zachary Fritts^a, Anastasia Vlasova^a, Linda J Saif^a and
4 Gireesh Rajashekara^{a*}

5 ^aCenter for Food Animal Health, Ohio Agricultural Research and Development Center,
6 Department of Animal Sciences, Ohio State University, 1680 Madison Avenue, Wooster,
7 OH 44691.

8 ^bGroup B-10: Biosecurity and Public Health, Bioscience Division, Los Alamos National
9 Lab, Los Alamos, NM 87545.

10

11 **Short Title:** Anti-rotavirus properties of probiotics

12

13

14

15 *Address correspondence to Dr. Gireesh Rajashekara DVM, PhD, Center for Food Animal
16 Health, Ohio Agricultural Research and Development Center, Department Animal
17 Sciences, Ohio State University, 1680 Madison Avenue, Wooster, OH 44691. E-mail
18 address: rajashekara.2@osu.edu

19

20

21

22

23

24 **Abstract**

25 Probiotics have been investigated to improve the universal rotavirus (RV) vaccination as
26 well as to ameliorate the RV infection. However, underlying mechanisms how probiotics
27 mediate beneficial effects needs more investigation. Thus, in the present study we used
28 polarized HT-29 cells to assess the anti-RV properties of Gram positive, G+ (*Lactobacillus*
29 *acidophilus*, *Lacticaseibacillus rhamnosus* GG, and *Bifidobacterium subsp. Lactis* Bb12)
30 and Gram negative, G- (*Escherichia coli* Nissle 1917) probiotics and study their underlying
31 mechanisms. Our results showed that pre-treatment of HT-29 cells for 4 hours with
32 probiotics, significantly reduced ($p < 0.05$) human RV replication and this effect was most
33 pronounced for *E. coli* Nissle followed by *L. acidophilus* and *L. rhamnosus* GG. Strikingly,
34 only pre-treatment with live bacteria or their supernatants demonstrated anti-RV
35 properties. Except Gram negative *E. coli* Nissle, the Gram-positive probiotics tested did
36 not bind to RV. Ingenuity Pathway Analysis of tight junction (TJ)- and innate immune-
37 associated genes indicated that *E. coli* Nissle or *E. coli* Nissle+RV treatments improved
38 cell-cell adhesion and cell contact, while *L. acidophilus* or *L. acidophilus*+RV treatments
39 also activated cell-cell contact but inhibited cell movement functions. RV alone inhibited
40 migration of cells event. Additionally, *E. coli* Nissle activated pathways such as the innate
41 immune and inflammatory responses via production of TNF, while RV infection activated
42 NK cells and inflammatory responses. In conclusion, *E. coli* Nissle's ability to bind RV,
43 modulate expression of TJ events, innate immune and inflammatory responses, via specific
44 upstream regulators may explain superior anti-RV properties of *E. coli* Nissle. Therefore,
45 prophylactic use of *E. coli* Nissle might help to reduce the RV disease burden in infants in
46 endemic areas.

47

48 **Keywords:** Rotavirus, HT-29 cells, *E. coli* Nissle, probiotics, tight junction, innate
49 immune response

50

51 **Introduction**

52 Infectious gastroenteritis is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in infants
53 worldwide. Rotavirus (RV) induced gastroenteritis is one such vaccine preventable disease
54 associated with 215,000 deaths annually worldwide in 2013 [1]. Several factors, including
55 malnutrition, micronutrient deficiencies, breastfeeding, maternal immunity, histo-blood
56 group antigen type, composition of gut microbiota and medication use have been suggested
57 to reduce efficacy of enteric vaccines in developing countries [2-9]. Typical symptoms
58 include vomiting, watery diarrhea, and fever. The fecal-oral route is the established mode
59 of transmission. Upon ingestion, RV infects mature small intestinal enterocytes and leads
60 to diarrhea via: i) destruction of enterocytes, ii) downregulation of the absorptive enzymes,
61 iii) inflammation of the gut and iv) compromised gut barrier [10,11]. Thus, an efficacious
62 and universal treatment to prevent or alleviate RV diarrhea in infants must be capable of:
63 i) regulating immune responses (inflammation), ii) restoring barrier functions, iii)
64 stimulating enterocyte proliferation and repair, and iv) inhibiting RV replication in the gut.

65 Probiotics represent a potential universal anti-RV treatment and thus, their effects are
66 being studied widely in combination with vaccines, antibiotics, and/or oral rehydration
67 therapies in clinical and animal studies [12-18]. Most of the probiotics are Gram-positive
68 (G+) bacteria; therefore, a wealth of literature regarding probiotic effects on amelioration
69 of RV disease is derived from bacterial species that belong to *Lactobacillus* and

70 *Bifidobacterium* genera [16]. The clinical efficacy of probiotic *Lactobacillus. acidophilus*
71 against RV was demonstrated in infants where *L. acidophilus* treatment resulted in
72 decreased severity of RV disease, characterized by improved stool consistency and reduced
73 duration of diarrhea [19-21]. Similarly, in randomized clinical trials *Lacticaseibacillus*
74 *rhamnosus* GG administration was shown to shorten the duration of RV diarrhea in
75 children [21, 22,23]. Further, prophylactic supplementation of *L. rhamnosus* LGG reduced
76 the risk of nosocomial diarrhea and rotavirus gastroenteritis in infants[24]. In a clinical
77 study that compared probiotic treatment to oral rehydration therapy, children consuming
78 probiotic *Bifidobacterium subsp. lactis* exhibited significantly reduced duration of RV
79 diarrhea [25]. Our group and others have demonstrated that *L. acidophilus*, *L. rhamnosus*
80 GG and *B. lactis* Bb12 were efficacious in reducing the severity of RV diarrhea in the
81 gnotobiotic piglet model [13,16,18,26]. However, the Gram negative probiotic *Escherichia*
82 *coli* Nissle-1917 has not been tested for anti-RV properties in infants [27], although several
83 animal studies from our group highlighted its superior characteristics compared to other
84 Gram positive probiotics in ameliorating RV disease [13,14,18]. A randomized, double-
85 blind clinical trial indicated that administration of *E.coli* Nissle successfully alleviated the
86 idiopathic chronic constipation without any major side effects[28].

87 Despite cumulative evidence of extensively evaluated Gram positive and Gram
88 negative probiotics in clinical and animal studies[13], their anti-RV properties and
89 mechanistic insights are poorly investigated [29]. Therefore, the objectives of this study
90 were to: i) investigate and compare anti-RV properties of Gram-positive probiotics (*L.*
91 *rhamnosus* GG, *L. acidophilus*, *B. animalis subsp. lactis* Bb12) and Gram-negative
92 probiotic (*E. coli* Nissle-1917), and ii) investigate the mechanisms by which *E. coli* Nissle

93 modulates rotavirus infections *in vitro*. Numerous cell lines have been used to investigate
94 the *in vitro* mechanisms of probiotics. The distinct features of human colonic
95 adenocarcinoma (HT-29) cells closely mimicking the *in vivo* functional intestinal
96 epithelium [30-34] make the HT-29 cells an ideal model. These differentiated cells possess
97 apical brush border proteins, Cl⁻ channels, Cl⁻ secretion, mucus production,
98 disaccharidases and peptidases, domes on impermeable substrates, trans-epithelial
99 resistance (TER) and intracellular tight junction proteins similar to intestinal epithelium.
100 In this study, we have established a polarized HT-29 cell monolayer model to investigate
101 anti-RV properties of the above-mentioned probiotics. We tested three different probiotic
102 treatment regimens to determine their effects on RV infection. (1) Pre-inoculation: This
103 approach mimics the *in vivo* effects of probiotics administered prior to RV infection as a
104 prophylactic measure in humans. (2) Co-inoculation: This regimen was used to model
105 probiotic administration during ongoing RV infections in infants. (3) Pre-incubation and
106 co-inoculation: Our rationale was that incubating RV with probiotics would provide
107 sufficient time to induce structural and functional alterations that would not be possible in
108 the direct co-inoculation experiment. Of the four probiotics tested in this study, *E. coli*
109 Nissle 1917 (Dr. Ulrich Sonnenborn) pre-treatment exhibited the most prominent anti-RV
110 properties, while *L. acidophilus* (ATCC 700396) and *L. rhamnosus* GG (ATCC-53103)
111 induced intermediate and the least effects, respectively. *E. coli* Nissle's superior anti-RV
112 properties were attributed to its ability to bind RV, modulate expression of TJ, innate
113 immune response and PRR signaling genes, via specific upstream regulators.

114

115 **Materials and methods**

116 **Bacteria and virus culturing**

117 Probiotic bacteria *E. coli* Nissle 1917 (Dr. Ulrich Sonnenborn, Department of Biological
118 Research, Ardeypharm GmbH, Germany) was cultured in Luria Bertani (Becton,
119 Dickinson and Company, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA) while, *Lacticaseibacillus rhamnosus*
120 GG, ATCC-53103, *Lactobacillus acidophilus* NCFM™ (ATCC 700396) and
121 *Bifidobacterium animalis subsp. lactis* Bb12 (Chr. Hansen Inc. Milwaukee, WI, USA)
122 were cultured in De Man, Rogosa and Sharpe (Becton, Dickinson and Company, Franklin
123 Lakes, NJ, USA) media and enumerated as described previously [35,36]. The virulent
124 human RV Wa G1P [8] strain at pig passages 25–26 was used in this study[37].

125

126 **Culturing of polarized HT-29 cells**

127 A unique feature of HT-29 cells observed in the absence of glucose and presence of
128 galactose is that the cells closely mimic the *in vivo* enterocyte architecture. Therefore, in
129 the present study we adapted previously established protocols to induce HT-29 polarization
130 [31-33]. Briefly, HT-29 cells (ATCC HTB-38™) were cultured in Dulbecco's modified
131 Eagle's medium (Invitrogen, Grand Island, NY, USA) containing 4.5 g/L D-glucose
132 (SigmaAldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS)
133 (Gibco, Amarillo, Texas, USA), 2 mM glutamine, 1% non-essential amino acids (Gibco,
134 Amarillo, Texas) and streptomycin-penicillin antibiotic (SigmaAldrich, St. Louis, MO)
135 mix for 2 days. Subsequently, cells were cultured in DMEM with gradually decreasing
136 concentrations of D-glucose (4 mM, 3 mM, 2 mM) with other cell culture ingredients added
137 daily as mentioned above. After that, the cells were cultured in the presence of 1 mM
138 glucose and 1 mM galactose (SigmaAldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) for 24 hours before

139 replacing glucose source from medium. In subsequent days, galactose source was gradually
140 increased in 1 mM increments to reach the final concentration of 5 mM with other
141 ingredients. Finally, the cells were sub-cultured to from monolayer and freezer stocks of
142 polarized HT-29 cells were prepared using routine cell culture techniques. Transmission
143 electron microscopy (TEM) was carried as described previously[38] at the Molecular and
144 Cellular Imaging Center (<http://www.oardc.ohio-state.edu/mcic>) to confirm the
145 polarization of the HT-29 cells. Here and onward, all *in vitro* experiments (unless specified
146 otherwise) were performed using the polarized HT-29 monolayers in 96 or 48-wells plates
147 with passage number ranging from P1 to P13. Each treatment including controls were
148 performed in triplicate wells in 2 to 3 independent experiments. Average mean and
149 standard deviation were used to express the results.

150

151 **Probiotics-HT-29 cells adhesion assay**

152 *E. coli* Nissle, *L. rhamnosus* GG, *L. acidophilus*, and *B. lactis* Bb12, were tested to assess
153 their cell adhesion properties after 30- and 60-minutes of incubation using multiplicity of
154 infections (MOI) 0.01 as described previously [39]. HT-29 cells were washed with
155 Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (DPBS) without CaCl₂ and MgCl₂ (Invitrogen,
156 Grand Island, NY, USA) 2-times and maintained in the cell culture medium without FBS
157 for 2 hours. Bacterial cultures were pelleted at 10,000 ×g for 10 minutes and washed with
158 antibiotic-free cell culture medium. Desired OD_{600nm} for different probiotic bacteria were
159 adjusted in antibiotic-free cell culture medium according to the established standard curve
160 (OD_{600nm} *E. coli* Nissle ~0.10, *L. rhamnosus* GG ~0.16, *L. acidophilus* ~0.23 and *B. lactis*
161 Bb12 ~0.78) that corresponds to MOI of 0.01. HT-29 cells were inoculated with bacterial

162 cells resuspended in antibiotic free cell culture media in triplicate wells. *E. coli* K-12 strain
163 (OD_{600nm} ~0.10) and the cell culture medium were included as controls. At the end of the
164 assay, media were carefully removed, and the cell monolayers were washed 2 times using
165 the cell culture medium with antibiotics. The HT-29 cells were then lysed with 0.1%
166 Triton-100X and suspension was used for colony forming unit (CFU) enumeration.

167

168 **RV infection of polarized HT-29 cells**

169 Earlier studies have demonstrated that RV can effectively infect HT-29 cells[40]. However,
170 the efficacy of RV replication could be affected by HT-29 polarization status and RV
171 strains used, which prompted us to determine the optimal conditions for RV infection in
172 HT-29 cells. The infectivity of RV Wa strain to polarized HT-29 cells was evaluated using
173 10-fold dilutions [1×10^8 to 1×10^3 focus forming units (FFU/mL)] of RV Wa RV infection
174 and quantification were measured as described previously[41].

175

176 **Probiotic treatment regimens**

177 We tested three different probiotic treatment regimens (pre-inoculation, co-inoculation,
178 and pre-incubation and co-inoculation) to determine their effects on RV infection. (1) Pre-
179 inoculation: This approach mimics the *in vivo* effects of probiotics administered prior to
180 RV infection as a prophylactic measure in humans. Our rationale was since probiotic
181 treatment induces beneficial changes in the host cells by up-regulating innate immune and
182 tight junction genes that would either prevent or inhibit RV replication. (2) The co-
183 inoculation: This regimen was used to model probiotic administration during ongoing RV
184 infections in infants. Our hypothesis was that probiotic and RV may share similar binding

185 sites on HT-29 cells, and thus probiotics could interfere with RV binding when probiotics
186 were mixed with the RV particles and then allowed to infect HT-29 cells simultaneously.
187 (3) Pre-incubation and co-inoculation: Our rationale was that incubating RV with
188 probiotics would provide sufficient time to induce structural and functional alterations that
189 would not be possible in direct co-inoculation experiment. We expected that direct
190 interactions between probiotics and RV may alter ligand/receptor expression needed for
191 productive infection of HT-29 cells.

192 (a) Pre-inoculation; probiotic bacteria to HT-29 cell ratio 100:1 was used to pretreat the
193 HT-29 cell monolayers for 1, 2 and 4 hours prior to RV Wa infection. (b) Co-inoculation;
194 RV and probiotic bacteria were mixed at the ratio of 1:100 and were used to inoculate the
195 HT-29 cells. (c) Pre-incubation/co-inoculation; a 1:100 mixture of RV and probiotic
196 bacteria was prepared and incubated at room temperature for 1 and 2 hours. At respective
197 time interval, suspension was used to infect HT-29 cells.

198

199 **Optimizing probiotic cells killing**

200 The cyclic freezing-thawing was used to kill the probiotic cells to better preserve the outer
201 membrane structure compared to dry heat killing. For this, 5 mL of OD adjusted bacterial
202 culture were frozen (-80° C) for 24, 48, 72 hours and 1-week time interval and followed by
203 thawing (37° C) at each time point and an aliquot of culture was used to enumerate the
204 number of live bacterial cells on the respective solid agar. Increasing freeze-thaw cycles (7
205 freeze cycles for 1-week incubation) decreased the number of live cells but it did not result
206 in 100% loss of viability. Thus, the dry heat killing method was used to conduct the
207 experiment. The dry heat-killing protocol was optimized for these probiotics incubating at

208 different temperatures and for variable durations. The lowest temperature and the shortest
209 duration that resulted in 100% loss of viability were selected to ensure that the bacterial
210 outer membrane surface architecture was preserved as much as possible. The optimal
211 condition was achieved for *E. coli* Nissle using 65° C for 5 minutes [42] and for *L.*
212 *acidophilus*, *L. rhamnosus* GG and *B. lactis* Bb12 using 65° C for 10 minutes. These
213 conditions were used throughout the study. Killed bacteria were pre-incubated with the
214 HT-29 cells for 4 hours to determine the anti-RV effects.

215

216 **Probiotic-RV binding using flow cytometry**

217 Binding of probiotics to RV was determined by flow cytometry as described previously
218 [13]. Briefly, probiotic bacteria stained with 5 µM SYTO 9 (Life technologies, Carlsbad,
219 CA, USA), followed by incubation with semi purified RV or Alexa Fluor 647 (Life
220 Technologies, Carlsbad, CA)–conjugated rotavirus like particles (VLP) at 37° C for 1.5
221 hours. The unbound virus particle on the probiotic bacteria were removed by washing 3
222 times with sterile PBS and bacteria were incubated with Alexa Fluor 647–conjugated anti-
223 RV mAb (clone RG23B9C5H11) or isotype control at 4°C for 45 minutes. The samples
224 were washed and bacterial-RV complexes were acquired using BD Accuri C6 flow
225 cytometer (Ann Arbor, MI, USA).

226

227 **Selection of probiotics and *in vitro* strategy to investigate anti-RV effects**

228 Unlike co-incubation strategies, pre-incubation of probiotic has a number of advantages to
229 demonstrate the probiotics anti-RV properties like: (i) probiotics can induce host innate
230 and adaptive responses like defensins, anti-microbial peptides, etc. that might prevent or

231 inhibit RV infection, (ii) probiotics can up-regulate tight junction proteins like ZO1,
232 Occludin thereby improve gut barrier function resulting in prevention/inhibition of RV
233 infection, and (iii) probiotics that are strongly adhered to host cells might even compete or
234 interfere with RV binding activity. Because of these advantages and as expected, outcome
235 of different probiotic treatment strategies led us to investigate the mechanisms regulating
236 probiotic effects using the pre-incubation regimen. We have focused on evaluating two
237 probiotics (*E. coli* Nissle and *L. acidophilus*) that showed significant anti-RV properties
238 compared to other two probiotics when incubated for 4 hours.

239

240 **Effect of *E. coli* Nissle and *L. acidophilus* pretreatment on HT-29 cells**

241 Prior to conducting the experiments, we assessed the cytotoxicity of *E. coli* Nissle and *L.*
242 *acidophilus* pre-treatment. The total number of cells and % dead cells were compared to
243 no probiotic treatment at 0 and 4 hours using conventional trypan blue staining technique.

244

245 **Effects of *E. coli* Nissle and *L. acidophilus* supernatant on RV infection**

246 Bacterial culture supernatants were harvested to determine their contribution to the
247 observed anti-RV properties of *E. coli* Nissle and *L. acidophilus*. Briefly, overnight grown
248 probiotic culture was centrifuged for 10,000 X g for 10 minutes to collect the supernatants.
249 Collected supernatants were filtered through 0.22-micron filter to generate cell-free
250 extracts. Further, portions of the original filtrates were used to prepare 10X filtrates using
251 vacuum concentrator (Thermo Fischer Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Instrument was
252 run on low vacuum mode to preserve any labile molecule until one tenth of volume

253 remained. *In vitro* pre-incubation experiment was performed at 4 hours of treatment with
254 1X and 10X cell-free extract as described above.

255

256 **RT² Profiler™ PCR Arrays Analysis**

257 The expressions of sets of 84 genes involved in each PCR arrays, i.e., Human Tight
258 Junction (TJ), Innate Immune Response were determined using RT² Profiler™ PCR Array
259 (Qiagen, Array # PAHS-143Z and PAHS-148Z, Germantown, MD, USA). The list of
260 genes, 96 well format, protocol used to perform these arrays can be found on Qiagen RT²
261 Profiler PCR array [42,43]. The gene list for TJ array included critical genes encoding
262 proteins that form impermeable barriers between epithelia cells to regulate polarity,
263 proliferation and differentiation ([https://www.qiagen.com/us/shop/pcr/primer-sets/rt2-
264 profiler-pcr-arrays?catno=PAHS-143Z#geneglobe](https://www.qiagen.com/us/shop/pcr/primer-sets/rt2-profiler-pcr-arrays?catno=PAHS-143Z#geneglobe)) while for, innate immune response and
265 PRR signaling included cellular growth and development, proliferation and maintenance,
266 and anti-inflammatory and pro-inflammatory responses and antimicrobial responses and
267 cell apoptosis- associated genes. HT-29 cells in 48 well tissue culture plates were treated
268 with *E. coli* Nissle and *L. acidophilus* for 4 hours and then infected with RV as described
269 previously[41]. Controls were included in the experiment: *E. coli* Nissle, *E. coli*
270 Nissle+RV, *L. acidophilus*, *L. acidophilus*+RV, and RV. Treated HT-29 cells were washed
271 and suspended in the TRIzol reagent (Life technologies, Carlsbad, CA USA). Total RNA
272 was extracted from the wells using the miRNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen, Germantown, MD)
273 and traces of DNA were removed using the Qiagen RT² First Strand Kit (Qiagen,
274 Germantown, MD, USA). The cDNA was synthesized using the Qiagen RT² First Strand
275 Kit and analyzed using RT² Profiler™ PCR Arrays. The Ct-values for each gene were

276 normalized using house-keeping genes that were included in the TJ and innate response
277 arrays. Subsequently, fold-changes in genes expression were determined using the $\Delta\Delta Ct$
278 method. To examine the potential functions and cellular pathways that were modulated in
279 HT-29 cells in response to different treatments, Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA; Qiagen,
280 Redwood City, CA, USA) was performed as described previously[44]. Each treatment was
281 performed in four replicate wells and was repeated in three independent experiments.

282

283 **Statistical analysis**

284 One-Way ANOVA followed by Sidak's multiple comparisons test was used for the
285 probiotic adhesion assay, while unpaired *t*-test was used to analyze the results of the RV
286 infection of HT-29 cells. The data generated in all other experiments were analyzed using
287 Two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons.
288 ANOVA was also used to analyze the qPCR data. A fold change of $\pm 1.5 \geq$ or ≤ 1.5 and a
289 *P*-value ≤ 0.05 was used to determine significant differences in the expression of the genes.
290 All the previous statistical analysis were performed using a GraphPad Prism software (San
291 Diego, CA). Significance level of the data analyzed in IPA was determined by default
292 Fisher's Exact test. In all statistical analysis a *p*-value of ≤ 0.05 was used to determine level
293 of significance.

294

295 **Results**

296 **Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) confirmed polarization of HT-29 cells**

297 HT-29 cells possessed both differentiated and undifferentiated epithelial cells of different
298 types including goblet cells, M cells, and enterocytes, more closely mimicking *in vivo*

299 conditions when grown in the presence of galactose [34, 45]. Thus, we adapted the above
300 protocol to induce HT-29 cells and confirmed the polarized state of HT-29 cells. TEM
301 imaging indicated that polarized HT-29 cells were characterized by presence of dense
302 granules, large vacuoles, tight junctions, and microvilli (**Figure 1 A; 1B**), closely
303 resembling the *in vivo* structure of intestinal epithelial cells.

304

305 **Probiotic bacteria adhere to HT-29 cells**

306 Probiotic bacteria like *B. lactis* Bb12 and *E. coli* Nissle were shown to adhere to epithelial
307 cell lines like Caco2; however, many factors are also known to influence the host cell
308 adhesion ability[46]. Thus, in the present study we confirmed the probiotic ability to adhere
309 to the HT-29 cells before investigating their anti-RV properties. Compared to 30 minutes
310 incubation (data not shown), higher numbers of bacterial cells adhered to HT-29 cells at
311 60 minutes. Gram negative bacteria *E. coli* Nissle and *E. coli* K-12 adhered more efficiently
312 to HT-29 cells compared to Gram positive probiotic bacteria (**Figure 2A**).

313 There were no significant differences in the binding ability of the Gram-positive probiotic
314 bacteria where 10% of bacterial cells were bound to HT-29 cells.

315

316 **RV infects polarized HT-29 cells**

317 Rhesus monkey kidney (MA104) cells are more commonly used for the growth and
318 characterization of both animal and human culture-adapted RVs. In addition to MA104
319 cells and depending upon the strain, RVs were shown to infect other types of continuous
320 cell lines including HT-29 cells[40, 47]. Our immediate question to answer was whether
321 polarized HT-29 cells are equally efficiently infected by RV Wa strain used in our present

322 study. Concurrent with previous findings, RV Wa strain infected polarized HT-29 cells,
323 but to some degree less efficiently compared to MA104 cells. MOI of RV Wa strain for
324 MA104 cells varied from 0.1 to 0.5 while HT-29 cells required 1 to 0.1 MOI [47]. Infection
325 with either 1.E+07 and 1.E+06 FFU of RV resulted in comparable number of FFU (**Figure**
326 **2B**); therefore, we used 1.E+07 FFU for our subsequent infections. Interestingly no RV
327 was detected when infected with lower than 1.0E+06 FFU.

328

329 **Pre- and co-inoculation with *E. coli* Nissle, *L. rhamnosus* GG and *L. acidophilus*** 330 **inhibited RV replication in HT-29 cells**

331 Except *B. lactis* Bb-12, other probiotic pretreatments significantly ($p < 0.05$) inhibited RV
332 replication in HT-29 cells (**Figure 3A**). Irrespective of *E. coli* Nissle pre-treatment
333 duration, RV Wa replication was inhibited, although most inhibition was observed at 4
334 hours of pre-treatment. While comparable trends were observed for *L. acidophilus* and *L.*
335 *rhamnosus* GG, the magnitude of the inhibition was lower, and reached significance only
336 at 4 hours of pre-treatment (**Figure 3A**). In the co-inoculation treatment, an overall similar
337 trend was observed with pre-treatment, wherein co-incubation with *E. coli* Nissle, *L.*
338 *acidophilus* and *L. rhamnosus* GG for 4 hours resulted in significant RV inhibition in HT-
339 29 cells (**Figure 3B**). As observed with pre-treatment above, *B. lactis* Bb12 co-inoculation
340 did not affect RV replication (**Figure 3B**). In the pre-incubation and co-inoculation
341 regimen, like pre- and co-inoculation experiments, *E. coli* Nissle induced the most
342 significant inhibition of RV infection, followed by *L. acidophilus* and *L. rhamnosus* GG
343 that resulted in a slight numeric, but not significant inhibition. In contrast, *B. lactis* Bb12
344 incubation and co-inoculation resulted in significantly increased RV replication compared

345 to RV alone and other probiotic treatments (**Figure 3C**). Interestingly, RV alone infectivity
346 in HT-29 cells decreased progressively during incubation at room temperature, which
347 precluded us from performing the 4-hour incubation and co-inoculation experiment.

348

349 **Observed anti-RV effects of probiotics were induced by live bacteria**

350 To investigate the mechanisms of the probiotic effects, we first sought to understand
351 whether live probiotics are essential to induce the observed anti-RV effects. Except for *B.*
352 *lactis* Bb-12, pre-treatment with other live probiotics resulted in inhibition of RV as
353 observed previously. However, this effect was not observed when heat-killed bacteria were
354 used. Neither live nor dead *B. lactis* Bb-12 pre-treatment resulted in RV inhibition (**Figure**
355 **4A**).

356

357 **Only *E. coli* Nissle binds to RV but not *L. acidophilus*, *L. rhamnosus* GG and *B. lactis*** 358 **Bb12**

359 The ability of probiotics to directly bind RVs is one of the mechanisms that contributes to
360 the anti-RV properties as we reported previously[13]. Therefore, we investigated the
361 probiotics-RV binding properties. Less than 2% of *L. acidophilus* and *B. lactis* Bb12 bound
362 to RV (**Figure 4B**), while significantly higher percentages (15%) of *E. coli* Nissle bind to
363 RV and no RV binding by *L. rhamnosus* GG was evident.

364

365 ***E. coli* Nissle and *L. acidophilus* pre-treatments did not result in cytotoxic effects in** 366 **HT-29 cells**

367 Increasing duration of probiotic treatment is generally not recommended due to rapid
368 multiplication of bacteria that ultimately damage the host cell monolayer. In our present
369 study, except for *E. coli* Nissle, probiotic treatments did not induce any monolayer
370 alterations. After, 4 hours of treatment, *E. coli* Nissle induced up to 50% HT-29 cells
371 monolayer clumping, which raised a question whether the observed superior anti-RV
372 effects of *E. coli* Nissle were due to the loss of host cells viability resulting in reduced
373 numbers of HT-29 cells available for RV infection. To address this concern, we determined
374 the total number of cells and % dead cells. There was no difference in the total numbers
375 and viability of HT-29 cells compared to no probiotic treatment controls. This suggests that
376 the observed anti-RV effects were due to probiotic induced alterations of the cell
377 physiology and/or structure (**Figure 5A**).

378

379 **Both *E. coli* Nissle and *L. acidophilus* culture supernatants possess anti-RV properties**

380 To establish if probiotic secreted factors present in culture supernatant induce beneficial
381 host responses to prevent or interfere with RV replication in HT-29 cells, we assessed the
382 effects of pretreatment with 1X and 10X cell free culture supernatants prepared from
383 probiotics grown in their respective media[35,36]. Both 1X and 10X *E. coli* Nissle and *L.*
384 *acidophilus* supernatants possessed RV inhibitory properties; however, there were no
385 differences between pre-treatment with 1X and 10X *E. coli* Nissle and *L. acidophilus*
386 supernatants. This suggests that *E. coli* Nissle and *L. acidophilus* secrete biologically active
387 molecules essential for the observed anti-RV effects (**Figure 5B**).

388

389 **Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA)**

390 To further study the mechanisms of the *E. coli* Nissle and *L. acidophilus* anti-RV
391 properties, we performed targeted PCR arrays and compared the fold-change expression of
392 genes in HT-29 cells in probiotic (*E. coli* Nissle, *L. acidophilus*, *E. coli* Nissle+RV and *L.*
393 *acidophilus* +RV) and RV infection alone treated groups (**Table S1 and S2** and **Figure S1**
394 **and S4**). A comprehensive summary of gene regulations was depicted as radar diagrams
395 (**Figure 6 and 11**). The IPA tool was used to predict the biological functions by analyzing
396 networks and canonical pathways. The top two gene regulatory networks associated with
397 *E. coli* Nissle, *L. acidophilus*, RV, *L. acidophilus* +RV and *E. coli* Nissle+ RV based on
398 focus molecules and scores are shown in **Table 1**.

399

400 **RV has limited influence on TJ gene functions and pathways compared to either of** 401 **probiotic treatments**

402 RV influenced a limited number of pathways compared to probiotic and probiotic+RV
403 treatments. For example, RV did not influence the electric resistance, transmigration of
404 granulocytes (lymphocyte and neutrophil) functions (**Figure 7A**). Correspondingly only
405 leucocyte excavation and PTEN signaling were affected by RV treatment (**Figure 7B**).
406 Paxillin signaling, which is involved in cell adhesion, was activated only by *E. coli* Nissle
407 or *E. coli* Nissle+RV but not in other treatments. *E. coli* Nissle or *E. coli* Nissle+RV
408 affected the most functions and pathways compared to others. Interestingly, *L. acidophilus*
409 +RV treatment activated functions and pathways that were not affected by RV treatment
410 alone. Though RV treatment influenced the function and pathways the least, it affected the
411 greatest number of upstream regulators compared with that of probiotic or probiotic+RV
412 treatments. The one upstream regulator CDX2, was only influenced by probiotic+RV

413 treatment (**Figure 7C**). CDX2 is a nuclear transcriptional factor involved in intestinal cell
414 proliferation, differentiation, adhesion, and apoptosis. Overall, *E. coli* Nissle or *E. coli*
415 Nissle+RV treatment affected several biological functions and cellular pathways while RV
416 alone influenced the least. The important TJ gene clusters that were differentially regulated
417 on RV and probiotics alone (*E. coli* Nissle and *L. acidophilus*) or probiotic +RV (*E. coli*
418 Nissle+RV, and *L. acidophilus* +RV) treatments are indicated in **Table 2**.

419

420 ***E. coli* Nissle treatment improves cell-cell adhesion and cell contact**

421 The five major predicted TJ cellular functions affected by the *E. coli* Nissle treatment alone
422 included: cell polarity formation, cell-cell contact, formation of adherens junctions, cell
423 movement, and cell-cell adhesion, wherein more specifically, cell-cell adhesion and cell
424 contact biological functions were highly activated while, cell polarity was least activated
425 (**Figure S2**). The genes like ACTN1&4, AFDN, Alpha Actinin, CTNNA3, ERK1/2,
426 JAM3, and MAGI1 lead to activation of cell-cell contact while, AFDN, Alpha catenin,
427 CTNNA3, and MAGI1 genes are responsible for the activated biological function of cell-
428 cell adhesion. A complete list of genes involved in the respective biological functions is
429 highlighted in **Figure S2**. Similar cellular pathways (cell polarity formation, cell-cell
430 contact, cell-cell adhesion, polarity of cells, formation of adherens junctions, and cell
431 movement) were affected in *E. coli* Nissle+RV treated cells; however, one additional
432 pathway was also influenced i.e., polarity of cells. Though all cellular pathways were
433 activated, cell-cell contact, and polarity of cells were highly triggered (**Figure 8**). The
434 polarity of cells was activated due to ACTN4, F Actin, JAM3, and PRKCZ genes while

435 the cell-cell contact was activated via ACTN1, ACTN4, AFDN, Alpha catenin, ERK1/2,
436 MAGI1, and Par6 genes.

437

438 **Cell-cell contact activated while cell movement inhibited on *L. acidophilus* treatment**

439 Affected cellular functions by the LA treatment alone included: cell polarity formation,
440 cell-cell contact, organization of cytoskeleton, formation of cellular protrusions, formation
441 of adherens junctions, and cell-cell adhesion. All the cellular functions were activated of
442 which, cell-cell contact, and cell-cell adhesion were highly stimulated by the LA treatment
443 (**Figure S3**). Genes involved in the respective cellular functions are illustrated in **Figure**
444 **S3**. The genes ACTN1, AFDN, Alpha Catenin, CTNNA3, and MAGI1 simultaneously
445 activated the functions of cell-cell contact and cell-cell adhesion (**Figure S3**). While after
446 LA+RV treatment, formation of tight junctions, cell polarity formation, cell-cell contact,
447 formation of adherens junctions, cell movement, formation of intercellular junctions, and
448 polarity of cells were affected (**Figure 9**). Compared to other cellular functions, cell-cell
449 contact, and cell movements were highly activated or inhibited, respectively. The activated
450 function of cell-cell contact was due to AFDN, ERK1/2, JAM3, and MPDZ genes while
451 inhibited cell movement function was due to AFDN, CLDN19, CLDN5, LLGL1, MAGI2,
452 PARD3, and PATJ genes (**Figure 9**).

453

454 **The migration of cells is inhibited on RV infection**

455 Six TJ biological functions like formation of tight junctions, cell-cell contact, cell-cell
456 adhesion, formation of intercellular junctions, morphology of tight junctions, and
457 migration of cells were modulated on RV infection of HT-29 cells, wherein most of the

458 functions were activated except migration of cells (**Figure 10**). The inhibited function of
459 migration of cells was associated with AFDN, AMOTL1, CLDN19, Cr3, LLGL1, and
460 MAGI1 genes (**Figure 10**).

461

462 **Innate functions and pathways not affected by RV were influenced in the presence of** 463 ***E. coli* Nissle treatment**

464 Since only *E. coli* Nissle showed significantly higher RV binding characteristics, innate
465 response PCR array was analyzed for *E. coli* Nissle and control groups but not for LA
466 group (**Figure 11, Figure S4, and Table S2**). One function of innate genes not affected by
467 RV, i.e., differentiation of blood cells, was influenced on *E. coli* Nissle or *E. coli*
468 Nissle+RV treatments (**Figure 12A**). Similarly, LPS stimulated MAPK, B cell receptor,
469 PI3K in B lymphocytes, PI3K/AKT, role of NFAT, Nf-kB, LXR/RXR, Ga12/13 signaling
470 were only influenced in the presence of *E. coli* Nissle treatments suggesting *E. coli* Nissle
471 activates robust innate immune responses (**Figure 12B**). For upstream regulators, RV
472 influenced all the regulators but with lesser intensity compared with *E. coli* Nissle or *E.*
473 *coli* Nissle+RV treatments (**Figure 12C**). The important innate gene clusters that were
474 differentially regulated on RV and *E. coli* Nissle alone or *E. coli* Nissle+RV treatments are
475 indicated in **Table 3**.

476

477 ***E. coli* Nissle activates innate immunity and inflammatory response via TNF** 478 **production**

479 The top 5 biological functions that were affected on *E. coli* Nissle treatment alone
480 included: production of cytokines, production of proteins, innate immune responses,

481 function of dendritic cells, and function of phagocytes (**Figure S5**). All the functions were
482 activated, and the genes involved in activating these functions in turn activated the robust
483 production of TNF. On *E. coli* Nissle+RV treatment, six biological functions that were
484 affected included, inflammatory response, cytokine and chemokine mediated signaling
485 pathway, cell movement of granulocytes, immune response of cells, activation of
486 phagocytes, and activation of macrophages (**Figure 13**). Interestingly, activation of
487 phagocytes and inflammatory responses were highly activated. The genes involved in the
488 activation of inflammatory response include CXCL8, Cpla2, Eotaxin, Ifn, Ifn gamma, LBP,
489 Pro-inflammatory, and Tnf (family) genes. The detailed list of genes involved and their
490 status in respective biological pathways can be found in **Figure 13**.

491

492 **NK cells and inflammatory response are strongly activated on RV infection**

493 Eight biological functions were affected on RV infection alone i.e., activation of cells,
494 inflammatory response, innate immune responses, production of cytokines, function of
495 antigen presenting cells, activation of natural killer (NK) cells, replication of virus, and
496 antiviral response (**Figure 14**). Of these, activation of NK cells and inflammatory
497 responses were strongly activated, and the genes involved in both these functions are in
498 **Figure 14**.

499

500 **Discussion**

501 Understanding interactions among pathogens, probiotics and host epithelial cells are of
502 utmost importance to maintain enteric health. In this study we utilized polarized HT-29
503 cells as an *in vitro* model to investigate the anti-RV properties of the selected Gram positive

504 and Gram-negative probiotics and their underlying mechanisms. The Gram positive and
505 Gram-negative probiotics were tested for their ability to inhibit RV replication using
506 established three-way treatment strategies mainly pre-inoculation, co-inoculation and pre-
507 incubation/co-inoculation. The *E. coli* Nissle and *L. acidophilus* in a pre-inoculation
508 strategy showed significantly higher ability to prevent RV replication in HT-29 cells. In
509 agreement with our findings, recent studies also highlighted the RV inhibitory effects of
510 probiotics like *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* species using *in vitro* cell culture system
511 [48-50], wherein up to 50% reduction in plaque forming units (PFU) was observed. Yet in
512 another study, six different *Bifidobacterium* strains were tested for anti-RV activity using
513 both HT-29 and MA-104 cell lines and showed up to 50% reduction in PFU, and further
514 higher RV reduction was evident in HT-29 cells compared to MA-104 cells, more
515 specifically in a pre-inoculation strategy [51]. Like previous studies, our findings
516 confirmed the ability of the *Lactobacillus* probiotics (*L. acidophilus* and *L. rhamnosus* GG)
517 to reduce RV replication and showed that the pre-inoculation strategy was more efficient
518 in reducing RV load in the HT-29 cells. Although the exact reasons for the lack of effects
519 of Bb12 treatment is unknown; factors like, probiotic strain and/ or species-specific effects,
520 RV strain used, dose and duration of probiotic treatment, etc., can undoubtedly influence
521 the experimental outcome.

522 Pre-inoculation of HT-29 cells with probiotics was more efficient in inhibiting RV in
523 our present study and from others' studies [48,50,52-54,55]. This strategy has numerous
524 advantages including: (i) limiting the cell adsorption and internalization of RV due to the
525 direct trapping of the virus by the probiotic bacteria [13,53,56], (ii) "cross-talk" with the
526 host epithelial cells in establishing antiviral protection [44,53,54,56], (iii) enhancing gut

527 mucosal barrier thereby reducing permeability [14,55], (iv) production of metabolites with
528 direct antiviral properties [53,56] and (v) interfering with intracellular RV replication by
529 regulating NSP4 and Ca²⁺ [50,52]. Interestingly, anti-RV effects were not observed when
530 dead probiotic cells were used (**Figure 4A**). However, RV replication inhibition was still
531 evident when cell culture supernatants were used (**Figure 5B**) in the pre-inoculation
532 regimen suggesting that live probiotics cells and their secreted products are necessary to
533 provide the RV inhibition effects. In this regards, recent studies have demonstrated that *E.*
534 *coli* Nissle supernatant contain both soluble proteins and outer membrane vesicles that
535 positively modulate the epithelia barrier through upregulation and redistribution of TJ
536 proteins mainly, ZO-1, ZO-2 and CLDN14[57,58]. Similarly, in our study both *E. coli*
537 Nissle and *L. acidophilus* pretreatment upregulated the expression of CLDN 14 (**Table 2**).
538 The probiotic's ability to bind RV particles was also shown to contribute to the anti-RV
539 properties. In the present and in our previous study [13], none of the tested probiotics other
540 than *E. coli* Nissle possessed any significant RV binding properties (**Figure 4B**). This
541 further suggests that the direct binding of RV particles by *E. coli* Nissle is an important
542 mechanism by which the reduction in RV replication is achieved following *E. coli* Nissle
543 treatment. Additionally, *E. coli* Nissle decreased cell movements and increased cell-to-cell
544 contact and TJ formation (**Figure 8 and S2**), the critical cellular functions that are
545 important for RV proliferation in the intestinal cells. Previous study has shown that in
546 polarized MDCK cells RV infection activates RhoA/ROCK/MLC signaling, which alters
547 TJ protein distribution and disrupts TJ integrity thereby facilitating RV access to
548 coreceptors and entry into the cells[59]. Though no specific activation of MLC signaling
549 was observed, we found that RV-induced inhibition of morphology of TJ and formation of

550 TJ/intercellular junctions (**Figure 9**). Inhibition of these TJ formation events help RV to
551 readily access the TJ and adherence junction's proteins that acts as receptors or coreceptors
552 for RV infection[60,61]. Specifically, JAM-A, occludin and ZO-1 of TJ proteins play
553 important receptor or coreceptor roles during RV entry into the cells[60]. Our study reports
554 that upregulation of JAM2 gene by RV infection, which to a certain extent was repressed
555 on probiotic treatments (**Table 2**). Another gene CLDN14 critical for TJ formation is
556 highly expressed after *E. coli* Nissle and LA treatments (**Table 2**) suggesting roles for these
557 probiotics in improving TJ formation[62]. Previously, *E. coli* Nissle was shown to induce
558 protein kinase C- ζ (PKC ζ) and extracellular-signal-regulated kinase 1/2 (ERK1/2)
559 phosphorylation mediated events to upregulate the TJ protein claudin-14 [62]. Further we
560 found that transcription factor 2 (CDX2), which is critical in early intestinal differentiation
561 and has been implicated as a master regulator of intestinal homeostasis and permeability is
562 only regulated and inhibited by probiotic+RV infection (**Figure 7**) suggesting the tested
563 probiotics likely negate the RV-induced intestinal inflammation and perturbed
564 homeostasis[63].

565 As predicted, *E. coli* Nissle modulated the expression of key genes involved in the
566 innate immune and inflammatory responses. TLR genes like TLR1, TLR5, and NOD1 were
567 upregulated on *E. coli* Nissle treatment (**Figure 9 and Table 3**). It is likely that *E. coli*
568 Nissle may antagonize the RV induced inhibition of NF- κ B pathway, as it was previously
569 reported that RV employs several strategies to inhibit immune responses in cells,
570 specifically the prevention of the nuclear accumulation of NF- κ B [64]. Another protein,
571 encoded by the RELA gene, is also uniquely upregulated by *E. coli* Nissle treatment (**Table**
572 **3**). This protein forms a dimer with NF- κ B in the nucleus and acts as the transcription factor

573 for many of the genes that are regulated by NF- κ B [65]. The upregulation of RELA by *E.*
574 *coli* Nissle treatment supports the idea that *E. coli* Nissle can boost the transcription of
575 genes regulated by NF- κ B, which are inhibited by RV. Interestingly, TNF was highly
576 upregulated by *E. coli* Nissle treatment. Besides the implications of higher levels of TNF
577 for the inflammatory response, TNF is known to recruit proteins that interact with RIPK1,
578 causing it to promote cell survival via the activation of the NF- κ B pathway [66]. Other
579 mechanisms that *E. coli* Nissle exploits to antagonize RV infection include, the
580 enhancement of antiviral sensing in HT-29. The protein encoded by the CARD6 gene (also
581 uniquely upregulated by *E. coli* Nissle; **Table 3** and **Figure 9**) has been shown to play a
582 key role in recognition of intracellular viral dsRNA [67]. Since RV is a dsRNA virus, and
583 if *E. coli* Nissle treated cells have an enhanced ability to detect the presence of RV, then
584 host cells may have an enhanced ability to mount a virus specific attack and/or signal other
585 cells about the presence of RV.

586

587 **Conclusion**

588 Taken together, our *in vitro* study, that represents a simplified model for probiotic-RV-
589 epithelial cell interactions, demonstrated that the probiotic *E. coli* Nissle acts via multiple
590 mechanisms: (i) RV binding, (ii) up-regulation of critical TJ genes via specific upstream
591 regulator (e.g., CDX2) to maintain gut barrier homeostasis, and (iv) activation of innate
592 immune and inflammatory responses to neutralize RV infection. Our *in vitro* findings
593 further suggest that *E. coli* Nissle supplementation, especially prior to enteric infections in
594 infants, can confer more benefits in reducing enteric infectious diseases.

595

596 **Acknowledgements**

597 This work was supported by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (OPP 1117467), the
598 NIAID, NIH (R01 A1099451), federal and state funds appropriated to the Ohio
599 Agricultural Research and Development Center, The Ohio State University and from the
600 NIH Office of Dietary Supplements (ODS) supplemental grant funds. Authors thank Dr.
601 Sukumar Kandasamy and Tea Meulia for their technical assistance in performing rotavirus
602 binding assay and electron microscopy imaging, respectively.

603

604 **Compliance with Ethical Standards**

605 **Conflict of Interest:** The authors declare no conflict of interest.

606 **Consent for Publication:** Not applicable

607 **Data availability:** All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this
608 published article (and in supplementary information files).

609 Author contributions: AK and GR conceptualize the study. AK, YH, and ZF performed
610 the experiments and analyze the data. AK, YH, and ZF prepared the original draft of the
611 manuscript. AK, YH, AV, LS, and GR reviewed and edited the manuscript. All authors
612 have acknowledged the final version of the manuscript.

613

614 **References**

- 615 1. Tate JE, Burton AH, Boschi-Pinto C, Parashar UD, World Health Organization-
616 coordinated global rotavirus surveillance (2016) Global, regional, and national
617 estimates of rotavirus mortality in children <5 years of age, 2000-2013. Clin Infect Dis
618 62 Suppl 2:S96-S105. <https://doi:10.1093/cid/civ1013>
619 2. Chen MY, Kirkwood CD, Bines J, Cowley D, Pavlic D, Lee KJ, Orsini F, Watts E,
620 Barnes G, Danchin M (2017) Rotavirus specific maternal antibodies and immune
621 response to RV3-BB neonatal rotavirus vaccine in New Zealand. Hum Vaccin
622 Immunother 13 (5):1126-1135. <https://doi:10.1080/21645515.2016.1274474>

- 623 3. Chilengi R, Simuyandi M, Beach L, Mwila K, Becker-Dreps S, Emperador DM,
624 Velasquez DE, Bosomprah S, Jiang B (2016) Association of maternal immunity with
625 rotavirus vaccine immunogenicity in Zambian infants. PloS One 11 (3):e0150100.
626 <https://doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0150100>
- 627 4. Groome MJ, Moon SS, Velasquez D, Jones S, Koen A, van Niekerk N, Jiang B,
628 Parashar UD, Madhi SA (2014) Effect of breastfeeding on immunogenicity of oral
629 live-attenuated human rotavirus vaccine: a randomized trial in HIV-uninfected infants
630 in Soweto, South Africa. Bull World Health Organ 92 (4):238-245.
631 <https://doi:10.2471/BLT.13.128066>
- 632 5. Harris VC, Armah G, Fuentes S, Korpela KE, Parashar U, Victor JC, Tate J, de Weerth
633 C, Giaquinto C, Wiersinga WJ, Lewis KDC, de Vos WM (2017) Significant
634 correlation between the infant gut microbiome and rotavirus vaccine response in rural
635 Ghana. J Infect Dis 215 (1):34-41. <https://doi:10.1093/infdis/jiw518>
- 636 6. Iturriza-Gomara M, Cunliffe NA (2017) The gut microbiome as possible key to
637 understanding and improving rotavirus vaccine performance in high-disease burden
638 settings. J Infect Dis 215 (1):8-10. <https://doi:10.1093/infdis/jiw521>
- 639 7. Mwila K, Chilengi R, Simuyandi M, Permar SR, Becker-Dreps S (2017) Contribution
640 of maternal immunity to decreased rotavirus vaccine performance in low- and middle-
641 income countries. Clin Vaccine Immunol 24 (1):e00405-16.
642 <https://doi:10.1128/CVI.00405-16>
- 643 8. Sindhu KNC, Cunliffe N, Peak M, Turner M, Darby A, Grassly N, Gordon M, Dube
644 Q, Babji S, Praharaj I, Verghese V, Iturriza-Gomara M, Kang G (2017) Impact of
645 maternal antibodies and infant gut microbiota on the immunogenicity of rotavirus
646 vaccines in African, Indian and European infants: protocol for a prospective cohort
647 study. BMJ Open 7 (3):e016577. <https://doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2017-016577>
- 648 9. Twitchell EL, Tin C, Wen K, Zhang HS, Becker-Dreps S, Azcarate-Peril MA, Vilchez
649 S, Li GH, Ramesh A, Weiss M, Lei SH, Bui T, Yang XD, Schultz-Cherry S, Yuan LJ
650 (2016) Modeling human enteric dysbiosis and rotavirus immunity in gnotobiotic pigs.
651 Gut Pathog 8:51. <https://doi:10.1186/s13099-016-0136-y>
- 652 10. Greenberg HB, Estes MK (2009) Rotaviruses: from pathogenesis to vaccination.
653 Gastroenterology 136 (6):1939-1951. <https://doi:10.1053/j.gastro.2009.02.076>
- 654 11. Parashar UD, Nelson EAS, Kang G (2013) Diagnosis, management, and prevention
655 of rotavirus gastroenteritis in children. BMJ 347:f7204. <https://doi:10.1136/bmj.f7204>
- 656 12. Ahmadi E, Alizadeh-Navaei R, Rezai MS (2015) Efficacy of probiotic use in acute
657 rotavirus diarrhea in children: A systematic review and meta-analysis.
658 Caspian J Intern Med 6 (4):187-195. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26644891/>
- 659 13. Kandasamy S, Vlasova AN, Fischer D, Kumar A, Chattha KS, Rauf A, Shao L,
660 Langel SN, Rajashekara G, Saif LJ (2016) Differential effects of *Escherichia coli*
661 Nissle and *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* strain GG on human rotavirus binding, infection,
662 and B cell immunity. J Immunol 196 (4):1780-1789.
663 <https://doi:10.4049/jimmunol.1501705>
- 664 14. Paim FC, Langel SN, Fischer DD, Kandasamy S, Shao L, Alhamo MA, Huang HC,
665 Kumar A, Rajashekara G, Saif LJ, Vlasova AN (2016) Effects of *Escherichia coli*
666 Nissle 1917 and Ciprofloxacin on small intestinal epithelial cell mRNA expression in
667 the neonatal piglet model of human rotavirus infection. Gut Pathog 8:66.
668 <https://doi:10.1186/s13099-016-0148-7>

- 669 15. Vlasova AN, Chattha KS, Kandasamy S, Liu Z, Esseili M, Shao LL, Rajashekara G,
670 Saif LJ (2013) *Lactobacilli* and *Bifidobacteria* promote immune homeostasis by
671 modulating innate immune responses to human rotavirus in neonatal gnotobiotic pigs.
672 PloS One 8 (10):e76962. <https://doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0076962>
- 673 16. Vlasova AN, Kandasamy S, Chattha KS, Rajashekara G, Saif LJ (2016) Comparison
674 of probiotic *Lactobacilli* and *Bifidobacteria* effects, immune responses and rotavirus
675 vaccines and infection in different host species. Vet Immunol Immunopathol 172:72-
676 84. <https://doi:10.1016/j.vetimm.2016.01.003>
- 677 17. Vlasova AN, Paim FC, Kandasamy S, Alhamo MA, Fischer DD, Langel SN, Deblais
678 L, Kumar A, Chepngeno J, Shao L, Huang HC, Candelero-Rueda RA, Rajashekara G,
679 Saif LJ (2017) Protein malnutrition modifies innate immunity and gene expression by
680 intestinal epithelial cells and human rotavirus infection in neonatal gnotobiotic pigs.
681 mSphere 2 (2):e00046-17. <https://doi:10.1128/mSphere.00046-17>
- 682 18. Vlasova AN, Shao L, Kandasamy S, Fischer DD, Rauf A, Langel SN, Chattha KS,
683 Kumar A, Huang HC, Rajashekara G, Saif LJ (2016) *Escherichia coli* Nissle 1917
684 protects gnotobiotic pigs against human rotavirus by modulating pDC and NK-cell
685 responses. Eur J Immunol 46 (10):2426-2437. <https://doi:10.1002/eji.201646498>
- 686 19. Gaon D, Garcia H, Winter L, Rodriguez N, Quintas R, Gonzalez SN, Oliver G (2003)
687 Effect of *Lactobacillus* strains and *Saccharomyces boulardii* on persistent diarrhea in
688 children. Medicina (B Aires) 63 (4):293-298.
689 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/14518142/>
- 690 20. Lee DK, Park JE, Kim MJ, Seo JG, Lee JH, Ha NJ (2015) Probiotic bacteria, *B.*
691 *longum* and *L. acidophilus* inhibit infection by rotavirus *in vitro* and decrease the
692 duration of diarrhea in pediatric patients. Clin Res Hepatol Gastroenterol 39 (2):237-
693 244. <https://doi:10.1016/j.clinre.2014.09.006>
- 694 21. Simakachorn N, Pichaipat V, Rithipornpaisarn P, Kongkaew C, Tongpradit P,
695 Varavithya W (2000) Clinical evaluation of the addition of lyophilized, heat-killed
696 *Lactobacillus acidophilus* LB to oral rehydration therapy in the treatment of acute
697 diarrhea in children. J Pediatr Gastr Nutr 30 (1):68-72. <https://doi:10.1097/00005176-200001000-00020>
- 698 22. Guandalini S, Pensabene L, Abu Zikri M, Dias JA, Casali LG, Hoekstra H, Kolacek
699 S, Massar K, Micetic-Turk D, Papadopoulou A, de Sousa JS, Sandhu B, Szajewska H,
700 Weizman Z (2000) *Lactobacillus* GG administered in oral rehydration solution to
701 children with acute diarrhea: A multicenter European trial. J Pediatr Gastroenterol
702 Nutr 30 (1):54-60. <https://doi:10.1097/00005176-200001000-00018>
- 703 23. Majamaa H, Isolauri E, Saxelin M, Vesikari T (1995) Lactic acid bacteria in the
704 treatment of acute rotavirus gastroenteritis. J Pediatr Gastroenterol Nutr 20 (3):333-
705 338. <https://doi:10.1097/00005176-199504000-00012>
- 706 24. Szajewska H, Kotowska M, Mrukowicz JZ, Armanska M, Mikolajczyk W (2001)
707 Efficacy of *Lactobacillus* GG in prevention of nosocomial diarrhea in infants. J Pediatr
708 138 (3):361-365. <https://doi:10.1067/mpd.2001.111321>
- 709 25. Erdogan O, Tanyeri B, Torun E, Gonullu E, Arslan H, Erenberk U, Oktem F (2012)
710 The comparison of the efficacy of two different probiotics in rotavirus gastroenteritis
711 in children. J Trop Med 2012:787240. <https://doi:10.1155/2012/787240>
- 712 26. Chattha KS, Vlasova AN, Kandasamy S, Esseili MA, Siegismund C, Rajashekara G,
713 Saif LJ (2013) Probiotics and colostrum/milk differentially affect neonatal humoral
714

- 715 immune responses to oral rotavirus vaccine. *Vaccine* 31 (15):1916-1923.
716 <https://doi:10.1016/j.vaccine.2013.02.020>
- 717 27. Henker J, Laass M, Blokhin BM, Bolbot YK, Maydannik VG, Elze M, Wolff C,
718 Schulze J (2007) The probiotic *Escherichia coli* strain Nissle 1917 (EcN) stops acute
719 diarrhoea in infants and toddlers. *Eur J Pediatr* 166 (4):311-318.
720 <https://doi:10.1007/s00431-007-0419-x>
- 721 28. Mollenbrink M, Bruckschen E (1994) Treatment of chronic constipation with
722 physiologic *Escherichia coli* bacteria. Results of a clinical study of the effectiveness
723 and tolerance of microbiological therapy with the *E. coli* Nissle 1917 strain (Mutaflor).
724 *Med Klin (Munich)* 89 (11):587-593. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/7815986/>
- 725 29. Lievin-Le Moal V, Servin AL (2014) Anti-infective activities of *Lactobacillus* strains
726 in the human intestinal microbiota: from probiotics to gastrointestinal anti-infectious
727 biotherapeutic agents. *Clin Microbiol Rev* 27 (2):167-199.
728 <https://doi:10.1128/Cmr.00080-13>
- 729 30. Ciarlet M, Crawford SE, Estes MK (2001) Differential infection of polarized
730 epithelial cell lines by sialic acid-dependent and sialic acid-independent rotavirus
731 strains. *J Virol*. 75 (23):11834-11850. <https://doi:10.1128/Jvi.75.23.11834-11850.2001>
- 732 31. Cohen E, Ophir I, Ben Shaul Y (1999) Induced differentiation in HT29, a human
733 colon adenocarcinoma cell line. *J Cell Sci*. 112 (16):2657-2666.
734 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10413674/>
- 735 32. Hilgendorf C, Spahn-Langguth H, Regardh CG, Lipka E, Amidon GL, Langguth P
736 (2000) Caco-2 versus Caco-2/HT29-MTX co-cultured cell lines: Permeabilities via
737 diffusion, inside- and outside-directed carrier-mediated transport. *J Pharm Sci* 89
738 (1):63-75. [https://doi:10.1002/\(Sici\)1520-6017\(200001\)89:1<63::Aid-Jps7>3.0.Co;2-6](https://doi:10.1002/(Sici)1520-6017(200001)89:1<63::Aid-Jps7>3.0.Co;2-6)
- 739 33. Kreusel KM, Fromm M, Schulzke JD, Hegel U (1991) Cl⁻ secretion in epithelial
740 monolayers of mucus-forming human colon cells (Ht-29/B6). *Am J Physiol* 261
741 (4):C574-C582. <https://doi:10.1152/ajpcell.1991.261.4.C574>.
- 742 34. Le Bivic A, Hirn M, Reggio H (1988) HT-29 cells are an *in vitro* model for the
743 generation of cell polarity in epithelia during embryonic differentiation. *Proc Natl*
744 *Acad Sci U S A* 85 (1):136-140. <https://doi:10.1073/pnas.85.1.136>.
- 745 35. Kumar A, Drozd M, Pina-Mimbela R, Xu X, Helmy YA, Antwi J, Fuchs JR, Nislow
746 C, Templeton J, Blackall PJ, Rajashekara G (2016) Novel anti-*Campylobacter*
747 compounds identified using high throughput screening of a pre-selected enriched small
748 molecules library. *Front Microbiol* 7:405. <https://doi:10.3389/fmicb.2016.00405>
- 749 36. Xu X, Kumar A, Deblais L, Pina-Mimbela R, Nislow C, Fuchs JR, Miller SA,
750 Rajashekara G (2015) Discovery of novel small molecule modulators of *Clavibacter*
751 *michiganensis* subsp. *michiganensis*. *Front Microbiol* 6:1127.
752 <https://doi:10.3389/fmicb.2015.01127>
- 753 37. Azevedo MS, Yuan L, Pouly S, Gonzales AM, Jeong KI, Nguyen TV, Saif LJ (2006)
754 Cytokine responses in gnotobiotic pigs after infection with virulent or attenuated
755 human rotavirus. *J Virol* 80 (1):372-382. <https://doi:10.1128/JVI.80.1.372-382.2006>
- 756 38. Pina-Mimbela R, Madrid JA, Kumar A, Torrelles JB, Rajashekara G (2015)
757 Polyphosphate kinases modulate *Campylobacter jejuni* outer membrane constituents
758 and alter its capacity to invade and survive in intestinal epithelial cells *in vitro*. *Emerg*
759 *Microbes Infect* 4 (12):e77. <https://doi:10.1038/emi.2015.77>

- 760 39. Mawad A, Helmy YA, Shalkami AG, Kathayat D, Rajashekara G. (2018) *E. coli*
761 Nissle microencapsulation in alginate-chitosan nanoparticles and its effect on
762 *Campylobacter jejuni* *in vitro*. Appl microbiol and biotechnol 102(24):10675-10690.
763 <https://doi:10.1007/s00253-018-9417-3>
- 764 40. Superti F, Tinari A, Baldassarri L, Donelli G (1991) HT-29 Cells - a new substrate for
765 rotavirus growth. Arch Virol 116 (1-4):159-173. <https://doi:10.1007/Bf01319239>
- 766 41. Terrett LA, Saif LJ, Theil KW, Kohler EM (1987) Physicochemical characterization
767 of porcine parrotavirus and detection of virus and viral antibodies using cell culture
768 immunofluorescence. J Clin Microbiol 25 (2):268-272. [https://doi:
769 10.1128/jcm.25.2.268-272.1987.](https://doi:10.1128/jcm.25.2.268-272.1987)
- 770 42. Helmy YA, Kassem, II, Kumar A, Rajashekara G (2017) *In vitro* evaluation of the
771 impact of the probiotic *E. coli* Nissle 1917 on *Campylobacter jejuni*'s invasion and
772 intracellular survival in human colonic cells. Front Microbiol 8:1588.
773 <https://doi:10.3389/fmicb.2017.01588>
- 774 43. Helmy YA, Kassem, II, Rajashekara G (2021) Immuno-modulatory effect of
775 probiotic *E. coli* Nissle 1917 in polarized human colonic cells against *Campylobacter*
776 *jejuni* infection. Gut microbes 13 (1):1-16.
777 <https://doi:10.1080/19490976.2020.1857514>
- 778 44. Kumar A, Vlasova AN, Liu Z, Chattha KS, Kandasamy S, Esseili M, Zhang X,
779 Rajashekara G, Saif LJ (2014) *In vivo* gut transcriptome responses to *Lactobacillus*
780 *rhamnosus* GG and *Lactobacillus acidophilus* in neonatal gnotobiotic piglets. Gut
781 Microbes 5 (2):152-164. <https://doi:10.4161/gmic.27877>
- 782 45. Laboisse CL, Maoret JJ, Triadou N, Augeron C (1988) Restoration by polyethylene-
783 glycol of characteristics of intestinal differentiation in subpopulations of the human
784 colonic adenocarcinoma cell line HT29. Cancer Res 48 (9):2498-2504.
785 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/3281752/>
- 786 46. Rinkinen M, Westermarck E, Salminen S, Ouwehand AC (2003) Absence of host
787 specificity for *in vitro* adhesion of probiotic lactic acid bacteria to intestinal mucus.
788 Vet Microbiol 97 (1-2):55-61. [https://doi: 10.1016/s0378-1135\(03\)00183-4.](https://doi:10.1016/s0378-1135(03)00183-4)
- 789 47. Arnold MM, Patton JT (2011) Diversity of interferon antagonist activities mediated
790 by NSP1 proteins of different rotavirus strains. J Virol 85 (5):1970-1979.
791 <https://doi:10.1128/Jvi.01801-10>
- 792 48. Kang JY, Lee do K, Ha NJ, Shin HS (2015) Antiviral effects of *Lactobacillus ruminis*
793 SPM0211 and *Bifidobacterium longum* SPM1205 and SPM1206 on rotavirus-infected
794 Caco-2 cells and a neonatal mouse model. J Microbiol 53 (11):796-803.
795 <https://doi:10.1007/s12275-015-5302-2>
- 796 49. Lee DK, Park JE, Kim MJ, Seo JG, Lee JH, Ha NJ (2015) Probiotic bacteria, *B.*
797 *longum* and *L. acidophilus* inhibit infection by rotavirus *in vitro* and decrease the
798 duration of diarrhea in pediatric patients. Clin Res Hepatol Gastroenterol 39 (2):237-
799 244. <https://doi:10.1016/j.clinre.2014.09.006>
- 800 50. Olaya Galan NN, Ulloa Rubiano JC, Velez Reyes FA, Fernandez Duarte KP, Salas
801 Cardenas SP, Gutierrez Fernandez MF (2016) *In vitro* antiviral activity of
802 *Lactobacillus casei* and *Bifidobacterium adolescentis* against rotavirus infection
803 monitored by NSP4 protein production. J Appl Microbiol 120 (4):1041-1051.
804 <https://doi:10.1111/jam.13069>

- 805 51. Munoz JA, Chenoll E, Casinos B, Bataller E, Ramon D, Genoves S, Montava R,
806 Ribes JM, Buesa J, Fabrega J, Rivero M (2011) Novel probiotic *Bifidobacterium*
807 *longum* subsp. *infantis* CECT 7210 strain active against rotavirus infections. *Appl*
808 *Environ Microbiol* 77 (24):8775-8783. <https://doi:10.1128/AEM.05548-11>
- 809 52. Buccigrossi V, Laudiero G, Russo C, Miele E, Sofia M, Monini M, Ruggeri FM,
810 Guarino A (2014) Chloride secretion induced by rotavirus is oxidative stress-
811 dependent and inhibited by *Saccharomyces boulardii* in human enterocytes. *PloS One*
812 9 (6):e99830. <https://doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0099830>
- 813 53. Colbere-Garapin F, Martin-Latil S, Blondel B, Mousson L, Pelletier I, Autret A,
814 Francois A, Niborski V, Grompone G, Catonnet G, van de Moer A (2007) Prevention
815 and treatment of enteric viral infections: possible benefits of probiotic bacteria.
816 *Microbes Infect* 9 (14-15):1623-1631. <https://doi:10.1016/j.micinf.2007.09.016>
- 817 54. Gagnon M, Vimont A, Darveau A, Fliss I, Jean J (2016) Study of the ability of
818 *Bifidobacteria* of human origin to prevent and treat rotavirus infection using colonic
819 cell and mouse models. *PLoS One* 11 (10):e0164512.
820 <https://doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0164512>
- 821 55. Liu FN, Li GH, Wen K, Bui T, Cao DJ, Zhang YM, Yuan LJ (2010) Porcine small
822 intestinal epithelial cell line (IPEC-J2) of rotavirus infection as a new model for the
823 study of innate immune responses to rotaviruses and probiotics. *Viral Immunol* 23
824 (2):135-149. <https://doi:10.1089/vim.2009.0088>
- 825 56. Botic T, Klingberg TD, Weingartl H, Cencic A (2007) A novel eukaryotic cell culture
826 model to study antiviral activity of potential probiotic bacteria. *Int J Food Microbiol*
827 115 (2):227-234. <https://doi:10.1016/j.jfoodmicro.2006.10.044>
- 828 57. Alvarez CS, Badia J, Bosch M, Gimenez R, Baldoma L (2016) Outer membrane
829 vesicles and soluble factors released by probiotic *Escherichia coli* Nissle 1917 and
830 commensal ECOR63 enhance barrier function by regulating expression of tight
831 junction proteins in intestinal epithelial cells. *Front Microbiol* 7:1981.
832 <https://doi:10.3389/fmicb.2016.01981>
- 833 58. Wang H, Jatmiko YD, Bastian SE, Mashtoub S, Howarth GS (2017) Effects of
834 supernatants from *Escherichia coli* Nissle 1917 and *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* on
835 intestinal epithelial cells and a rat model of 5-fluorouracil-induced mucositis. *Nutr*
836 *Cancer* 69 (2):307-318. <https://doi:10.1080/01635581.2017.1263747>
- 837 59. Soliman M, Cho EH, Park JG, Kim JY, Alfajaro MM, Baek YB, Kim DS, Kang MI,
838 Park SI, Cho KO (2018) Rotavirus-induced early activation of the RhoA/ROCK/MLC
839 signaling pathway mediates the disruption of tight junctions in polarized MDCK cells.
840 *Sci Rep* 8 (1):13931. <https://doi:10.1038/s41598-018-32352-y>
- 841 60. Torres-Flores JM, Silva-Ayala D, Espinoza MA, Lopez S, Arias CF (2015) The tight
842 junction protein JAM-A functions as coreceptor for rotavirus entry into MA104 cells.
843 *Virology* 475:172-178. <https://doi:10.1016/j.virol.2014.11.016>
- 844 61. Dong D, Xie W, Liu M (2020) Alteration of cell junctions during viral infection.
845 *Thorac Cancer* 11 (3):519-525. <https://doi:10.1111/1759-7714.13344>
- 846 62. Hering NA, Richter JF, Fromm A, Wieser A, Hartmann S, Gunzel D, Bucker R,
847 Fromm M, Schulzke JD, Troeger H (2014) TpcC protein from *E. coli* Nissle improves
848 epithelial barrier function involving PKC ζ and ERK1/2 signaling in HT-29/B6 cells.
849 *Mucosal Immunol* 7 (2):369-378. <https://doi:10.1038/mi.2013.55>

- 850 63. Coskun M, Troelsen JT, Nielsen OH (2011) The role of CDX2 in intestinal
851 homeostasis and inflammation. *Biochim Biophys Acta* 1812 (3):283-289.
852 <https://doi:10.1016/j.bbadis.2010.11.008>
- 853 64. Holloway G, Truong TT, Coulson BS (2009) Rotavirus antagonizes cellular antiviral
854 responses by inhibiting the nuclear accumulation of STAT1, STAT2, and NF- κ B. *J*
855 *Virology* 83 (10):4942-4951. <https://doi:10.1128/jvi.01450-08>
- 856 65. Newton K, Dixit VM (2012) Signaling in innate immunity and inflammation. *Cold*
857 *Spring Harb Perspect Biol* 4 (3). <https://doi:10.1101/cshperspect.a006049>
- 858 66. Bertrand MJ, Vandenabeele P (2010) RIP1's Function in NF-kappaB activation: from
859 master actor to onlooker. *Cell Death Differ* 17 (3):379-380.
860 <https://doi:10.1038/cdd.2009.213>
- 861 67. Dufner A, Mak TW (2006) CARD Tricks: controlling the interactions of CARD6
862 with RICK and microtubules. *Cell Cycle* 5 (8):797-800.
863 <https://doi:10.4161/cc.5.8.2635>
864
- 865
- 866

867 **Figure legends**

868

869 **Fig. 1** TEM cross section images of induced HT-29 cells in presence of galactose and in
870 absence of glucose in cell culture medium. **(A)** 2K magnification and **(B)** 5K magnification
871 of selected image A, where arrows respectively indicate (a) dense granule (b) large vacuole
872 (c) tight junction and (d) microvillus presence

873

874 **Fig. 2 (A)** Probiotic adhesion assay confirms tested probiotics efficiently adhere to
875 polarized HT-29 cells after 60 minutes of incubation. EcN: *E.coli Nissle*, LA: *L.*
876 *acidophilus*, LGG: *L. rhamnosus* GG, and Bb12: *B.lactis*: Bb12. One-way ANOVA,
877 Sidak's multiple comparisons test where * refers to $p \leq 0.05$. **(B)** Wa RV strain infects
878 polarized HT-29 cells at MOIs 1 and 0.1. Unpaired t-test. ns; non-significant.

879

880 **Fig. 3** Probiotics treatment strategies to demonstrate the anti-RV properties **(A)** Pre-
881 inoculation, **(B)** Co- inoculation and **(C)** Incubation and inoculation. EcN: *E.coli Nissle*,
882 LA: *L. acidophilus*, LGG: *L. rhamnosus* GG, and Bb12: *B.lactis*: Bb12. Two-way
883 ANOVA, Tukey's multiple comparisons test where * refers to $p \leq 0.02$, ** refers to $p \leq$
884 0.002 , *** refers to $p \leq 0.0005$, **** refers to $p \leq 0.0001$, and ns refers to non-significant.

885

886 **Fig. 4 (A)** Assessment of dead bacterial cell effects on RV infection to HT-29 cells. EcN:
887 *E.coli Nissle*, LA: *L. acidophilus*, LGG: *L. rhamnosus* GG, and Bb12: *B.lactis*: Bb12. Two-
888 way ANOVA, Tukey's multiple comparisons test where * refers to $p \leq 0.02$, ** refers to p
889 ≤ 0.002 , *** refers to $p \leq 0.0005$, **** refers to $p \leq 0.0001$, and ns refers to non-significant.

890 (B) Probiotics RV binding ability assessed by flow cytometry. Two-way ANOVA, Tukey's
891 multiple comparisons test where ns refers to non-significant.

892

893 **Fig. 5 (A)** Cytotoxic effect of HT-29 cells evaluated by percentage of number of live and
894 dead cells on 4 hours of *E. coli* Nissle and *L. acidophilus* treatment. Two-way ANOVA,
895 Tukey's multiple comparisons test where ns refers to non-significant. **(B)** Effect of *E. coli*
896 Nissle and *L. acidophilus* culture supernatants (1X and 10X) on RV replication. Two-way
897 ANOVA, Tukey's multiple comparisons test * refers to $p \leq 0.04$.

898

899 **Fig. 6.** Fold change expression of TJ genes for different treatment groups were depicted in
900 the form of radar diagram by normalizing HT-29 cells basal level expressions. RV alone
901 infection resulted in increased expression of CLDN 8 and 19 genes that were some extents
902 reduced on *L. acidophilus* pre-treatment. Interestingly, MAGI2 gene expression was down
903 regulated on RV infection but not rescued by probiotics pre-treatment. Where EcN: *E.coli*
904 *Nissle*, LA: *L. acidophilus*.

905

906 **Fig. 7** An overall summary of TJ genes' IPA predicted **(A)** cellular functions, **(B)** their
907 corresponding pathways that are in turn regulated by **(C)** upstream regulators. The heatmap
908 shows the predicted activation (blue color) or inhibition (brown) of several selected cellular
909 functions for each of the treatment groups. The intensity of color correspondence to
910 expression status. The functions, pathways and upstream regulators are organized
911 descending of $-\log(p)$ values that represents the extent to which the gene set for a particular

912 group overlaps with the given cellular function/pathways. The red color arrows and a box
913 highlight unique signatures at each level. Where EcN: *E.coli Nissle*, LA: *L. acidophilus*.

914

915 **Fig. 8** Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA) predicted TJ cellular functions that are
916 consistently activated and inhibited on following *E. coli* Nissle+RV treatment. The
917 networks of differentially expressed genes were algorithmically generated based on their
918 connectivity such that the highly interconnected networks likely represent significant
919 biological function. The Fischer's exact test was used to calculate a P value for each
920 biological function assigned to a particular network. The name and number of molecules
921 involved are described in table.

922

923 **Fig. 9** Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA) predicted TJ cellular functions that are
924 consistently activated and inhibited on following LA+RV treatment. The networks of
925 differentially expressed genes were algorithmically generated based on their connectivity
926 such that the highly interconnected networks likely represent significant biological
927 function. The Fischer's exact test was used to calculate a P value for each biological
928 function assigned to a particular network. The name and number of molecules involved are
929 described in table.

930

931 **Fig. 10** Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA) predicted TJ cellular functions that are
932 consistently activated and inhibited on RV infection. The networks of differentially
933 expressed genes were algorithmically generated based on their connectivity such that the
934 highly interconnected networks likely represent significant biological function. The

935 Fischer's exact test was used to calculate a P value for each biological function assigned to
936 a particular network. The name and number of molecules involved are described in table.

937

938 **Fig. 11** Fold change expression of innate response genes for different treatment groups
939 were depicted in the form of radar diagram by normalizing HT-29 cells basal level
940 expressions. RV alone infection resulted in significant increase in expression of IFNB1 and
941 ZBP1 that were reduced on *E. coli* Nissle treatment. Where EcN: *E.coli Nissle*, LA: *L.*
942 *acidophilus*.

943

944 **Fig. 12** An overall summary of innate response genes' IPA predicted (A) cellular functions,
945 (B) their corresponding pathways that are in turn regulated by (C) upstream regulators. The
946 heatmap shows the predicted activation (blue color) or inhibition (brown) of several
947 selected cellular functions for each of the treatment groups. The intensity of color
948 correspondence to expression status. The functions, pathways and upstream regulators are
949 organized descending of $-\log(p)$ values that represents the extent to which the gene set for
950 a particular group overlaps with the given cellular function/pathways. The red color box
951 highlights the unique signatures at each level.

952

953 **Fig. 13** Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA) predicted innate response cellular functions that
954 are consistently activated and inhibited on following *E. coli* Nissle+RV treatment. The
955 networks of differentially expressed genes were algorithmically generated based on their
956 connectivity such that the highly interconnected networks likely represent significant
957 biological function. The Fischer's exact test was used to calculate a P value for each

958 biological function assigned to a particular network. The name and number of molecules
959 involved are described in table.

960

961 **Fig. 14** Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA) predicted innate response cellular functions that
962 are consistently activated and inhibited on following RV infection. The networks of
963 differentially expressed genes were algorithmically generated based on their connectivity
964 such that the highly interconnected networks likely represent significant biological
965 function. The Fischer's exact test was used to calculate a P value for each biological
966 function assigned to a particular network. The name and number of molecules involved are
967 described in table.

968

969 **Supplementary Figure Legends**

970 **Fig. S1** Total number of up/down regulated genes at different treatments in comparisons
971 to HT-29 cells basal levels of expression. Fold change cut off value of ± 1.5 was used to
972 count the total number of genes.

973

974 **Fig. S2** Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA) predicted TJ cellular functions that are
975 consistently activated and inhibited on *E. coli* Nissle alone treatment. The networks of
976 differentially expressed genes were algorithmically generated based on their connectivity
977 such that the highly interconnected networks likely represent significant biological
978 function. The Fischer's exact test was used to calculate a P value for each biological
979 function assigned to a particular network. The name and number of molecules involved are
980 described in table.

981

982 **Fig. S3** Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA) predicted TJ cellular functions that are
983 consistently activated and inhibited on *L. acidophilus* alone treatment. The networks of
984 differentially expressed genes were algorithmically generated based on their connectivity
985 such that the highly interconnected networks likely represent significant biological
986 function. The Fischer's exact test was used to calculate a P value for each biological
987 function assigned to a particular network. The name and number of molecules involved are
988 described in table.

989

990 **Fig. S4** Total number of up/down regulated genes at different treatments in comparisons
991 to HT-29 cells basal levels of expression. Fold change cut off value of ± 1.5 was used to
992 count the total number of genes.

993

994 **Fig. S5** Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA) predicted innate cellular functions that are
995 consistently activated and inhibited on *E. coli* Nissle alone treatment. The networks of
996 differentially expressed genes were algorithmically generated based on their connectivity
997 such that the highly interconnected networks likely represent significant biological
998 function. The Fischer's exact test was used to calculate a P value for each biological
999 function assigned to a particular network. The name and number of molecules involved are
1000 described in table.

1001

1002

1003

Table 1: Top gene regulatory networks associated with treatment of the HT-29 cells with *E.coli Nissle*, *L. acidophilus*, RV, *L. acidophilus* +RV and *E.coli Nissle*+ RV based on focus molecules and scores*

Tight junction			Innate immune response		
Top network involved	Score	Focus molecules	Top network involved	Score	Focus molecules
<i>E.coli Nissle</i>					
(1) Cell Morphology, Cell-To-Cell Signaling and Interaction, Cellular Assembly and Organization	58	23	(1) Cell Morphology, Cellular Function and Maintenance, Protein Synthesis	16	8
(2) Cell-To-Cell Signaling and Interaction, Cellular Assembly and Organization, Cellular Function and Maintenance	48	20	(2) Cell Death and Survival, Infectious Diseases, Organismal Survival	12	6
RV					
(1) Cell-To-Cell Signaling and Interaction, Cellular Assembly and Organization, Cellular Function and Maintenance	67	25	(1) Cell-To-Cell Signaling and Interaction, Infectious Diseases, Protein Synthesis	23	10
(2) Cellular Assembly and Organization, Cellular Function and Maintenance, Tissue Development	21	25	(2) Cell-To-Cell Signaling and Interaction, Cellular Movement, Inflammatory Response	15	7
<i>E.coli Nissle</i> + RV					
(1) Cell Morphology, Cellular Assembly and Organization, Cellular Function and Maintenance	65	25	(1) Cell-To-Cell Signaling and Interaction, Cellular Movement, Hematological System Development and Function	24	11
(2) Cell-To-Cell Signaling and Interaction, Cellular Assembly and Organization, Cellular Function and Maintenance	37	16	(2) Antimicrobial Response, Cell Death and Survival, Inflammatory Response	21	10
<i>L. acidophilus</i>			NA		

(1) Cell Morphology, Cellular Assembly and Organization, Cellular Development	55	22
(2) Cell-To-Cell Signaling and Interaction, Cellular Assembly and Organization, Cellular Function and Maintenance	40	17
<hr/>		
<i>L. acidophilus</i> + RV		NA
(1) Cell-To-Cell Signaling and Interaction, Cellular Assembly and Organization, Cellular Function and Maintenance	75	27
(2) Cardiovascular System Development and Function, Cell Morphology, Cell-To-Cell Signaling and Interaction	18	9
<hr/>		

*Only top networks are shown, where “score” reflects number of network eligible molecules; the higher scores indicate that the given network is more likely modulated by different treatment. Focus molecules are the affected genes in different treatments and were considered for generating networks. NA- Not applicable. Since only *E.coli* Nissle showed significantly higher RV binding characteristic, innate response PCR array was not analyzed for *L. acidophilus* or *L. acidophilus*+RV group.

Table 2: The fold change expressions of selected tight junction (TJ) genes in signaling pathways.

Gene symbol	Name	<i>E.coli</i> Nissle	<i>E.coli</i> Nissle+RV	<i>L.acidophilus</i>	<i>L.acidophilus</i> +RV	RV
CLDN14	Claudin-14	50.56		35.26	30.27	
CLDN19	Claudin-19	30.62	140.17	29.71	71.68	142.09
CLDN8	Claudin-8	33.81		31.45	48.42	326.40
CTNNB1	Catenin Beta 1	11.66	31.51	11.35	15.55	22.61
ICAM2	Intercellular adhesion molecule 2	8.16	10.00	7.92	5.62	16.61
JAM2	Junctional adhesion 2	2.66	13.04	2.96	5.55	7.48
JAM3	Junctional adhesion 3	2.84	2.76	2.80	1.95	
MAGI2	Membrane Associated Guanylate Kinase, WW And PDZ Domain Containing 2	59.71	-83.87	57.68	-3.66	-24.25
PARD6A	Par-6 Family Cell Polarity Regulator Alpha	2.89	1.82	2.85	1.51	
PARD6B	Par-6 Family Cell Polarity Regulator Beta	1.99	2.25	2.00	1.87	
TIAM1	T-lymphoma invasion and metastasis-inducing protein 1	103.97		67.18		-3.81

The fold change expressions were calculated using HT-29 cells basal level genes expressions, where a cutoff value of ± 1.5 -fold change was considered to tabulate.

Table 3: The fold change expressions of selected innate genes in signaling pathways.

Gene Symbol	Name	<i>E.coli</i> Nissle	<i>E.coli</i> Nissle+ RV	RV
AKT1	V-akt murine thymoma viral oncogene homolog 1	2.81	1.84	
CXCL8	Interleukin 8	4.68	6.54	2.22
CARD6	Caspase recruitment domain family, member 6	1.83	2.03	
CD14	CD14 molecule	2.84	1.55	
CXCL1	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 1 (melanoma growth stimulating activity, alpha)	17.44	17.55	13.94
IFNA1	Interferon, alpha 1			-1.51
IFNB1	Interferon, beta 1, fibroblast		2.34	18.75
IKBKB	Inhibitor of kappa light polypeptide gene enhancer in B-cells, kinase beta	1.80	1.63	
IRF5	Interferon regulatory factor 5	2.80	1.93	
IRF7	Interferon regulatory factor 7	2.23	1.86	4.00
NFKBIA	Nuclear factor of kappa light polypeptide gene enhancer in B-cells inhibitor, alpha	2.56	3.52	3.91
	Nucleotide-binding oligomerization domain-containing protein 1	2.16	2.81	1.98
NOD1				
RELA	V-rel reticulendotheliosis viral oncogene homolog A (avian)	2.49	2.42	
RIPK1	Receptor (TNFRSF)-interacting serine-threonine kinase 1	1.74	1.61	
TLR1	Toll like receptor 1	3.47	2.94	1.66

TLR5	Toll like receptor 5	8.07	5.53	2.83
TNF	Tumor necrosis factor	12.02	14.72	3.14

The fold change expressions were calculated using HT-29 cells basal level genes expressions, where a cutoff value of ± 1.5 -fold change was considered to tabulate.

Polarized cells

Figure 1

A**Figure 2**

A**Pre- inoculation****Figure 3**

A**Figure 4**

A**Figure 5**

Tight Junction Genes

Figure 7

Functions Annotation	p-Value	Molecules	# Molecules
Cell polarity formation	6.09E-09	JAM3,LLGL1,MARK2,PARD6A,PARD6B,PRKCZ	6
Cell-cell contact	9.78E-08	ACTN1,ACTN4,AFDN,Alpha catenin,ASH1L,atypical protein kinase C,CTNNA3,ERK1/2,F Actin,IGSF5,JAM2,JAM3,MAGI1,Par6,PARD6B,PRKCZ,SPTAN1	17
Cell-cell adhesion	0.00000931	AFDN,Alpha catenin,ASH1L,CTNNA3,ERK1/2,IGSF5,JAM2,JAM3,MAGI1	9
Polarity of cells	0.0000225	ACTN4,F Actin,JAM3,MARK2,PRKCZ	5
Formation of adherens junctions	0.0000352	AFDN,Alpha catenin,JAM3,PRKCZ	4
Cell movement	0.000198	ACTN1,ACTN4,AFDN,Alpha Actinin,Alpha catenin,AMOTL1,ASH1L,Cr3,CTNNA2,ERK1/2,F Actin,ICAM2,JAM2,JAM3,LLGL1,MAGI1,MAGI2,MARK2,PARD6B,PRKCZ	20

Figure 8

Functions Annotation	p-Value	Molecules	# Molecules
Formation of tight junctions	1.02E-10	atypical protein kinase C, CLDN19, CLDN4, CLDN5, Par6, PARD3, PARD6B, PRKCZ	8
Cell polarity formation	1.74E-10	JAM3, LLGL1, MARK2, PARD3, PARD6A, PARD6B, PRKCZ	7
Cell-cell contact	2.82E-07	AFDN, atypical protein kinase C, cldn, CLDN19, CLDN4, CLDN5, ERK1/2, IGSF5, JAM2, JAM3, MPDZ, Par6, PARD3, PARD6B, PRKCZ, SMURF1	16
Formation of adherens junctions	0.0000446	AFDN, JAM3, PRKCZ	3
Cell movement	0.000624	AFDN, CLDN19, CLDN4, CLDN5, Cofilin, Cr3, ERK1/2, ICAM2, JAM2, JAM3, LLGL1, MAGI2, MARK2, PARD3, PARD6B, PATJ, PLC gamma, PRKCZ, SMURF1	19
Formation of intercellular junctions	0.00000401	AFDN, atypical protein kinase C, CLDN19, CLDN4, CLDN5, Par6, PARD3, PARD6B, PRKCZ	9
Polarity of cells	0.0000309	Cofilin, JAM3, MARK2, PARD3, PRKCZ	5

Figure 9

Functions Annotation	p-Value	Molecules	# Molecules
Formation of tight junctions	6.23E-07	atypical protein kinase C,CLDN11,CLDN19,CLDN3,CLDN4	5
Cell-cell contact	0.0000089	AFDN,Alpha catenin,atypical protein kinase C,cldn,CLDN11,CLDN19,CLDN3,CLDN4,CTNNA3,ERK1/2,F	15
Cell-cell adhesion	0.000107	Actin,IGSF5,JAM2,MAGI1,MPDZ	8
Formation of intercellular junctions	0.000377	AFDN,atypical protein kinase C,CLDN11,CLDN19,CLDN3,CLDN4,F Actin	7
Morphology of tight junctions	0.000421	AFDN,CLDN11	2
Migration of cells	0.00121	AFDN,AMOTL1,CLDN11,CLDN19,CLDN3,CLDN4,CLDN7,Cr3,CTNNA2,ERK1/2,F Actin,ICAM2,JAM2,LLGL1,MAGI1,MAGI2,Pka	17

Figure 10

Innate Response Genes

Figure 11

A Functions

Proliferation of cells
 Organismal death
 Migration of cells
 Synthesis of nitric oxide
 Activation of cells
 Activation of leukocytes
 Proliferation of lymphatic system cells
 Differentiation of mononuclear leukocytes
 Inflammatory response
 Leukocyte migration
 Activation of lymphocytes
 Proliferation of lymphocytes
 Cell survival
 Proliferation of mononuclear leukocytes
 Production of reactive oxygen species
 Differentiation of phagocytes
 Recruitment of leukocytes
 Recruitment of phagocytes
 Cell transformation
 Recruitment of neutrophils
 Neoplasia of tumor cell lines
 Immune response of cells
 Stimulation of cells
 Quantity of cytokine
 Formation of osteoclasts
 Differentiation of blood cells
 Differentiation of monocytes
 Activation of T lymphocytes
 Differentiation of cells
 Activation of phagocytes
 Accumulation of neutrophils
 Adhesion of phagocytes
 Proliferation of immune cells

B Pathways

IL-6 Signaling
 Acute Phase Response Signaling
 IL-8 Signaling
 HMGB1 Signaling
 Colorectal Cancer Metastasis Signaling
 Role of Pattern Recognition Receptors in Recognition of Bacteria and Viruses
 Dendritic Cell Maturation
 PPAR Signaling
 Toll-like Receptor Signaling
 Production of Nitric Oxide and Reactive Oxygen Species in Macrophages
 Type I Diabetes Mellitus Signaling
 TREM1 Signaling
 RANK Signaling in Osteoclasts
 LPS/IL-1 Mediated Inhibition of RXR Function
 Activation of IRF by Cytosolic Pattern Recognition Receptors
 IL-1 Signaling
 TNFR1 Signaling
 LPS-stimulated MAPK Signaling
 B Cell Receptor Signaling

 Role of RIG1-like Receptors in Antiviral Innate Immunity
 NF-κB Signaling
 PPARα/RXRα Activation
 PI3K Signaling in B Lymphocytes
 Type II Diabetes Mellitus Signaling
 PI3K/AKT Signaling
 Role of NFAT in Regulation of the Immune Response
 NF-κB Activation by Viruses
 LXR/RXR Activation
 Ga12/13 Signaling

C Upstream regulators

TNF
 LY294002
 RELA
 lipopolysaccharide
 curcumin
 IFNG
 TLR4
 E. coli B5 lipopolysaccharide
 GF11
 F2
 poly rI:rC-RNA
 IL1A
 salmonella minnesota R595
 lipopolysaccharides
 miR-155-5p (miRNAs w/seed UAAUGCU)
 Interferon alpha
 camptothecin
 FN1
 phorbol myristate acetate
 IL1B
 TLR7
 TRAF6
 NFκB (complex)
 MAPK9
 P38 MAPK
 E. coli B4 lipopolysaccharide
 CD40LG
 TRADD
 NLRP12
 CSF2
 IL1RN
 resiquimod
 MYD88

Figure 12

C

Functions Annotation	p-Value	Molecules	# Molecules
Inflammatory response	2.9E-12	B-cell receptor,CAMP,CCL3,CD14,Cpla2,CXCL1,CXCL8,Eotaxin,ERK1/2,Ifn,Ifn gamma,Ige,IL12A,LBP,LCN2,MAP2K3,Nfat (family),NOD1,Pro-inflammatory Cytokine,PRTN3,SCAVENGER receptor CLASS A,Tnf (family)	22
Cytokine and chemokine mediated signaling pathway	8.34E-10	CCL3,CXCL1,CXCL8,IL12A,LBP,LCN2,PRTN3	7
Cell movement of granulocytes	1.65E-09	CAMP,CCL3,CD14,CXCL1,CXCL8,Eotaxin,ERK1/2,LBP,LCN2,PRTN3	10
Immune response of cells	1.76E-09	CAMP,CCL3,CD14,CXCL1,CXCL8,ERK1/2,Fcgr3,Ifn,Ifn gamma,IL12A,LCN2,NOD1,PRTN3,Tnf (family)	14
Activation of phagocytes	1.41E-11	CAMP,CCL3,CD14,CXCL1,CXCL8,ERK1/2,Fcer1,HLA-DR,Ifn,Ifn gamma,Ige,LBP,LCN2,MAP2K3,Pro-inflammatory Cytokine,PRTN3,SCAVENGER receptor CLASS A,Tnf (family)	18
Activation of macrophages	2.02E-09	CAMP,CCL3,CD14,CXCL8,ERK1/2,Ifn,Ifn gamma,Ige,LBP,LCN2,MAP2K3,Pro-inflammatory Cytokine,SCAVENGER receptor CLASS A,Tnf (family)	14

Figure 13

Functions Annotation	p-Value	Molecules	# Molecules
Activation of cells	3.73E-10	IFN alpha/beta,IFN type 1,IFNA1/IFNA13,Ifnar,IL-1R,IL12A,IRAK3,IRF7,Lymphotoxin,MHC Class I (complex),SLPI,TH1 Cytokine,TICAM1,Tlr,TLR1,TLR5, TNF, Tnf receptor,ZBP1	19
Inflammatory response	3.35E-09	IFN alpha/beta,IFN type 1,IFNA1/IFNA13,IL12A,IRAK3, Lymphotoxin,SLPI,TH1 Cytokine,TICAM1,Tlr,TLR1,TLR5, TNF,ZBP1	14
Innate immune response	1.27E-08	IFN alpha/beta,IFN type 1,IRAK3,IRF7,SLPI,Tlr,TLR1,TNF, Tnf receptor,ZBP1	10
Production of cytokine	1.73E-08	IRAK3,TICAM1,Tlr,TLR1,TLR5	5
Function of antigen presenting cells	3.63E-08	IFN type 1,IRAK3,SLPI,TICAM1,TLR1,TLR5,TNF	7
Activation of natural killer cells	6.28E-08	IFN alpha/beta,IFN type 1,IFNA1/IFNA13,IL12A,MHC Class I (complex),TICAM1,Tlr,TLR1,TNF	9
Replication of virus	2.63E-07	IFN alpha/beta,IFN type 1,IFNA1/IFNA13,Ifnar,IL12A,IRF7, Lymphotoxin,SLPI,TICAM1,TNF,ZBP1	11
Antiviral response	0.0000188	IFN alpha/beta,IFN type 1,IFNA1/IFNA13,IRF7,TH1 Cytokine,TICAM1,Tlr,TNF	8

Figure 14

Table S1: Fold change expressions of tight junction (TJ) genes.

Symbol	<i>E. coli</i> Nissle	<i>E. coli</i> Nissle+RV	<i>L.</i> <i>acidophilus</i>	<i>L. acidophilus</i> +RV	RV
ACTN1	1.91	2.67	1.91	1.92	
ACTN2	42.52	-1.51	30.48		-1.89
ACTN3	87.04	37.22	23.78	19.43	30.22
ACTN4	2.19	1.75		1.71	
AMOTL1	167.73	-5.94	162.02		-3.94
ASH1L		1.66			1.61
CASK				-1.51	
CD99	3.95	2.32	3.87	1.70	2.55
CGN	2.33	2.41	2.32	2.03	1.50
CLDN10	4.07	3.06	2.94	4.26	2.56
CLDN11	3.62	3.69	3.54		2.67
CLDN12				-1.51	-1.50
CLDN14	50.56		35.26	30.27	
CLDN15	2.21	1.50	2.19		1.81
CLDN16	-2.64	1.68			
CLDN17	135.30	-6.92	130.69		
CLDN18		2.23			2.94
CLDN19	30.62	140.17	29.71	71.68	142.09
CLDN3	2.36	1.68	2.32		3.02
CLDN4	1.61	2.20	1.61	1.58	-1.50
CLDN5	34.67		33.27	519.67	
CLDN6	11.32	50.93	11.00	27.05	41.86
CLDN7					-1.66
CLDN8	33.81		31.45	48.42	326.40
CLDN9	4.54	12.05	4.45	6.75	7.75
CRB1	33.59		8.46		
CSNK2A2	2.73	2.14	2.68	1.78	2.16
CTNNA2	18.05	28.24	17.47	15.53	20.85
CTNNA3	11.55	-2.48	11.16		-5.17
CTNNB1	11.66	31.51	11.35	15.55	22.61
CTTN	5.08	6.29	5.09	3.77	1.75
EPB41	2.01	2.09			2.24
ESAM	2.75	2.13	1.69	2.21	2.05
HCLS1	7.41	19.74	7.20	9.45	18.46
ICAM1	4.31	6.23	4.25	4.22	4.64
ICAM2	8.16	10.00	7.92	5.62	16.61
IGSF5	13.29	12.75	11.82	5.34	13.32
INADL				-2.15	
JAM2	2.66	13.04	2.96	5.55	7.48
JAM3	2.84	2.76	2.80	1.95	

LLGL1	9.91	9.63	9.69	5.99	6.99
LLGL2	7.57	9.18	7.40	5.47	6.57
MAGI1	2.79	3.14	2.73		4.76
MAGI2	59.71	-83.87	57.68	-3.66	-24.25
MARK2	6.96	30.66	6.83	16.51	20.49
MLLT4	1.93	2.51	1.92	1.77	1.98
MPDZ	42.92	156.62	41.50	80.48	190.09
PARD3				-2.01	
PARD6A	2.89	1.82	2.85	1.51	
PARD6B	1.99	2.25	2.00	1.87	
PECAM1	17.79	91.90	17.34	46.81	67.85
PRKCZ	7.01	23.33	6.99	11.46	20.81
SMURF1	2.61	4.68	2.61	3.02	1.93
SPTA1	15.35	-1.54	7.31		
SPTAN1	2.61	2.42	2.59	2.32	1.50
SYMPK	7.10	12.33	6.94	7.06	5.38
TIAM1	103.97		67.18		-3.81
TJAP1	3.97	4.35	3.98	3.19	2.45

Fold change were calculated using HT-29 cells basal level genes expressions, where a cutoff value of ± 1.5 -fold change was considered to tabulate.

Table S2: Fold change expressions of innate genes.

Gene Symbol	<i>E. coli</i> Nissle	<i>E. coli</i> Nissle+RV	RV
AKT1	2.81	1.84	
BIRC3	2.49	4.63	1.80
CAMP	-1.44	-1.69	
CARD6	1.83	2.03	
CARD9		2.14	
CASP1		1.94	
CCL3		-5.17	
CCL5	-2.18		4.63
CD14	2.84	1.55	
CXCL1	17.44	17.55	13.94
CXCL2	12.05	12.05	10.54
CXCL8	4.68	6.54	2.22
DMBT1	11.29		
HSP90AA1		1.93	1.66
IFNA1			-1.51
IFNB1		2.34	18.75
IKBKB		1.63	
IL6	1.64		
IL12A	1.80	2.94	1.64

IL12B	1.84		-4.37
IL1B	2.96	3.48	
IRAK3	2.15	15.66	1.66
IRF5	2.80	1.93	
IRF7	2.23	1.86	4.00
JUN	7.79	6.29	5.40
LBP		3.08	
LCN2	-2.11	-1.65	
LTF			1.93
MAP2K1	1.53	1.63	
MAP2K3		1.65	
MAPK8			1.47
MAPK14	1.61		
NFKBIA	2.56	3.52	3.91
NLRP3		-1.48	
NOD1	2.16	2.81	1.98
PRTN3		2.20	
PYCARD			1.64
RELA	2.49	2.42	
RIPK1	1.74	1.61	
SLC11A1		3.07	
SLPI			-1.66
SUGT1	-1.64	-1.61	
TRAF6			1.78
TICAM1	3.13	3.68	1.56
TICAM2	-3.26	-2.39	
TIRAP	1.85		
TLR1	3.47	2.94	1.66
TLR5	8.07	5.53	2.83
TNF	12.02	14.72	3.14
TNFRSF1A	1.79		
TOLLIP	1.84	1.50	1.89
ZBP1		5.90	16.76

Fold change expressions were calculated using HT-29 cells basal level genes expressions, where a cutoff value of ± 1.5 -fold change was considered to tabulate

Anti-rotavirus properties and mechanisms of selected Gram-positive and Gram-negative probiotics in polarized human colonic (HT-29) cells

Anand Kumar et al.,

Supplemental figures

Figure S1

Functions Annotation	p-Value	Molecules	# Molecules
Cell polarity formation	4.92E-11	CRB1,JAM3,LLGL1,MARK2,PARD6A,PARD6B,PRKCZ	7
Cell-cell contact	3.54E-07	ACTN1,ACTN4,AFDN,Alpha catenin,atypical protein kinase C,CTNNA3,ERK1/2,F Actin,IGSF5,JAM2,JAM3,MAGI1,Par6,PARD6B,PRKCZ,TIAM1	16
Formation of adherens junctions	0.0000272	AFDN,Alpha catenin,JAM3,PRKCZ	4
Cell movement	0.00005	Actin,ACTN1,ACTN4,AFDN,Alpha Actinin,Alpha catenin,AMOTL1,Cr3,CTNNA2,Dishevelled,ERK1/2,F Actin,ICAM2,JAM2,JAM3,LLGL1,MAGI1,MAGI2,MARK2,PARD6B,PRKCZ,Talin,TIAM1	23
Cell-cell adhesion	0.0000642	AFDN,Alpha catenin,CTNNA3,ERK1/2,IGSF5,JAM2,JAM3,MAGI1	8

Figure S2

Functions Annotation	p-Value	Molecules	# Molecules
Cell polarity formation	3.44E-11	CRB1,JAM3,LLGL1,MARK2,PARD6A,PARD6B,PRKCZ	7
Cell-cell contact	0.0000022	ACTN1,AFDN,Alpha catenin,atypical protein kinaseC,CTNNA3,ERK1/2,F Actin,IGSF5,JAM2,JAM3,MAGI1,Par6,PARD6B,PRKCZ,TIAM1	15
Organization of cytoskeleton	0.0000169	Actin,ACTN1,ACTN2,AFDN,atypical protein kinase C,calpain,CGN,Cr3,CTNNA2,ERK1/2,F Actin,LLGL1,MAGI2,MARK2,PARD6A,PARD6B,PRKCZ,TIAM1	18
Formation of cellular protrusions	0.0000174	Actin,ACTN2,AFDN,atypical protein kinase C,calpain,CTNNA2,ERK1/2,F Actin,LLGL1,MAGI2,MARK2,PARD6A,PARD6B,PRKCZ,TIAM1	15
Formation of adherens junctions	0.0000237	AFDN,Alpha catenin,JAM3,PRKCZ	4
Cell-cell adhesion	0.0000487	AFDN,Alpha catenin,CTNNA3,ERK1/2,IGSF5,JAM2,JAM3,MAGI1	8

Figure S3

Figure S4

Functions Annotation	p-Value	Molecules	# Molecules
Production of cytokine	1.39E-11	IRAK3,TICAM2,TIRAP,TLR1,TLR5	5
Production of protein	3.93E-08	IRAK3,TICAM2,TIRAP,TLR1,TLR5,TNF	6
Innate immune response	1.73E-07	DMBT1,IFN type 1,IRAK3,NLR,TIRAP,TLR1,TNF,Tnf receptor	8
Function of dendritic cells	5.75E-07	IFN type 1,IRAK3,TIRAP,TLR5,TNF	5
Function of phagocytes	7.18E-07	IFN type 1,IRAK3,TIRAP,TLR1,TLR5,TNF	6

Figure S5